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**ODISHA
STATE LEVEL ISTE
STUDENT ANNUAL CONVENTION**

3rd June 2023

**PROCEEDINGS OF NATIONAL SEMINAR
ON
“ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY OF PROFESSIONAL
STUDENT IN NATION BUILDING”**

Sponsored by

ISTE New Delhi

Jointly Organised by

Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar

&

ISTE (REC Chapter & Odisha Section)

Published by

Journal of Engineering Innovation & Research

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CHIEF MINISTER MESSAGE

NAVEEN PATNAIK
CHIEF MINISTER, ODISHA

LOKASEVA BHAVAN
BHUBANESWAR

MESSAGE

I am glad to know that the Department of Mechanical Engineering of Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and bringing out a proceedings on **“Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building”** in commemoration.

The seminar aims to bring together researchers, scientists, engineers, and scholars from various fields to discuss the role and responsibility of professional students in nation building. This forum invites scientists, engineers, and intellectuals from all fields of engineering and technology to share their unique ideas, and experiences to motivate the professionals to work towards the progress of the nation through involvement and hard work.

I extend my warm greetings to all the delegates in this significant event, and wish the program all success.

(NAVEEN PATNAIK)

MESSAGE

SRI CA. B. RAMPRASAD RAO

Chairman

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

I am delighted to know that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on **“Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building”**.

Participation of different personalities from the field of engineering, science and industries will definitely bring awareness among the participants and promote this to help the development of society and nation ultimately.

I hope the outcome from such type of seminar will benefit every stake holders and give our institution a new dimension.

I wish the program all success.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of a stylized 'R' followed by a horizontal line and a small flourish.

SRI CA. B. RAMPRASAD RAO

Chairman

MESSAGE

DR. MANOJ KUMAR PALO

Vice-Chairman

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

It gives me immense pleasure to know that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on “**Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building**”.

Dignitaries present in the forum will focus on role and responsibility of Professional Student in a wider way and inspire the participants to work for the society and nation. I hope this national seminar will disseminate and share elaborate knowledge and experiences in creating the awareness among the professionals for development of the nation.

I wish the national seminar all success.

Manoj Kumar Palo

DR. MANOJ KUMAR PALO

Vice Chairman

MESSAGE

DR. SARAD CHANDRA PANDA

Secretary

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

It gives me immense pleasure that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on “**Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building**”.

In fact this topic is quite relevant to the students, faculty members and in particular to the technical educational institutions. I hope the outcome of the seminar will inspire and motivate the participants. Such seminar will definitely add value to our institute.

I thank the organizers and wish the program a grand success.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'S. Panda', with a horizontal line underneath.

DR. SARAD CHANDRA PANDA

Secretary

MESSAGE

PROF. GOURI SANKAR MISHRA

Director (T & P)

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

It is truly giving me immense pleasure to know that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on “**Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building**”.

The subject matter is the need of the hour and quite helpful to the participants. The key point of the discussion made by the eminent personalities will give an insight to the students to enhance their knowledge and skill and help them to engross in their effort in nation building.

I wish the program a grand success.

PROF. G. S. MISHRA

PROF. GOURI SANKAR MISHRA

Director (T & P)

MESSAGE

PROF. RAMESH CHOUDHURY

Director (Admin & Finance)

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

I am delighted to know that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on **“Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building”**. I hope this seminar will definitely give an insight to the participants through discussions and suggestions and send a message to the professionals about their role and responsibility for the society and nation. The outcome of this seminar will help every participants to understand their roles for nation building.

I wish the program a grand success.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'RAMESH CHOUDHURY', with a stylized flourish above it.

PROF. RAMESH CHOUDHURY

Director (Admin & Finance)

MESSAGE

PROF. (DR.) BIMAL SARANGI

Principal

Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

I am glad to know that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and publish a proceedings on **“Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building”**. This forum will discuss extensively about the role and responsibility of the professionals through sharing the knowledge and experiences from the experts. I hope this seminar will bring a positive impact on participants to understand their responsibility and participation as individual for the development of the nation.

I thank the organizers and wish the program a grand success.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'B. Sarangi'.

PROF. (DR.) BIMAL SARANGI

PRINCIPAL

**INDIAN SOCIETY OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION
ODISHA SECTION**

MESSAGE

PROF PRAVAT KUMAR PARHI

**Chairman, ISTE Odisha Section & Professor, Civil Engg Deptt, OUTR
Bhubaneswar**

I am extremely delighted to learn that, Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar is organising the 24thISTE Students Convention of Odisha Section on 3rd June, 2023 and a State Level Seminar is also conducted on the theme topic, Role and Responsibility of Professional Students in Nation Building. I extend my special thanks and appreciation to the Management, Principal and the Organising Committee of the host institute for making all arrangements ready for organising the event most successfully. The Convention is indeed a big platform for the policy makers, academicians, ISTE faculty members, ISTE student members and the intellectuals to join in a common forum and deliberate their thoughts on the theme topic.

Students of the technical and professional institutes are required to be well trained with acquiring thorough knowledge in both theory and practice. Skilled and well trained students can only contribute for the development of the nation through their innovative thought process and zeal. I hope that, hundreds of participating students will be deeply motivated in the presence of invited subject experts with vast experience and knowledge base. I congratulate the Principal, Organising Secretary and the team members who have been instrumental in organizing the Convention with a grand success. I am sure that, the convention will meet the objectives and the expectations of the delegates and the stake holders. I wish the Convention, a grand success.

**Prof P K Parhi
Chairman, ISTE Odisha Section & Professor (OUTR)**

MESSAGE

PROF. UTTAM KUMAR JENA

Convener and Head, Department of CSE& Dean Students Welfare
Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

It gives me immense pleasure that Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and going to publish a proceedings on “**Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building**”. It is an opportunity provided by ISTE REC Chapter & Odisha section in association Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar to bring together professors, students and personalities from industries to share their experiences with participants to give a light on role and responsibility of professionals for the nation building. .

I wish the proceeding all success.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'Uttam Kumar Jena', written over a horizontal line.

PROF. UTTAM KUMAR JENA

Convener

MESSAGE

PROF. (DR.) RANJAN KISHORE MALLICK

Co-Convener and Head, Department of Mechanical Engineering
Raajdhani Engineering College, Bhubaneswar

It gives me immense pleasure that our Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar is organizing an **Odisha State Level ISTE Student Annual Convention** on 3rd June 2023 and going to publish a proceedings on “**Role and Responsibility of Professional Student in Nation Building**”. I hope this program will aims at focusing on role and responsibility of professionals for nation building. The experts from the Institute and industry will share their knowledge to help and motivate the younger professionals to understand their role and become a part for the nation development.

I am very much thankful to the national advisory members of this seminar, Management, Faculty members, Supporting staff and Students to make this national seminar a grand success.

I wish the proceeding all success.

RKMallik

PROF. (DR.) RANJAN KISHORE MALLICK
Co-Convener

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR TEACHERS IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION

Dr. Bimal Sarangi

Principal, Raajdhani Engineering College Bhubaneswar, Odisha, www.rec.ac.in

What is exactly artificial intelligence (AI)?

The replication of human intelligence functions by machines, particularly computer systems, is known as artificial intelligence. Expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition, and machine vision are some examples of specific AI applications.

Basic process: Through the development and use of algorithms integrated into a dynamic computing environment, artificial intelligence (AI) provides the foundation for simulating human intelligence processes. Simply said, AI aims to emulate human thought and behaviour in machines.

What students will get? : With AI, students receive an immediate system-generated response rather of waiting for feedback from the instructor, which helps them learn a topic, recall their mistakes, and also how to do it correctly the next time. The

function of the teacher could be altered by AI.

In technical education, AI has the potential to significantly improve teaching and learning. Here are a few ways AI can be used to assist technical education teachers:

1. **Personalised Learning:** To create individualised learning environments, AI may analyse student data including performance, learning preferences, and learning styles. Teachers can make use of adaptive learning platforms driven by AI that provide personalised content, pacing, and feedback based on the needs of specific students.

2. **Intelligent Tutoring Systems:** AI can serve as an intelligent tutor who offers pupils real-time direction and help. In order to assist students comprehend technical concepts and effectively solve issues, these systems can provide step-by-step explanations, interactive simulations, and quick feedback.

3. **Automated Grading:** AI can automate grading, especially for tasks and tests that include multiple-choice or objective questions. By doing this, teachers may spend more time giving students individualised feedback and collaborating with them on higher-level work.

4. Content Recommendations: Based on the particular requirements and interests of individual students, AI can suggest pertinent learning materials, textbooks, videos, or online courses. This makes it easier for teachers to add to their curriculum and guarantees that students have access to a wide variety of materials of the highest calibre.

5. Virtual Laboratories and Simulations: Students can gain practical experience in technical areas like computer programming, engineering, or scientific experiments through the use of AI-powered virtual laboratories and simulations. These resources can be used by teachers to improve experiential learning and let pupils investigate ideas.

6. Data Analytics and Insights: Artificial intelligence (AI) can analyse vast volumes of data to spot patterns and trends in student performance, engagement, and learning outcomes. These insights can be used by teachers to plan lessons carefully, spot areas for development, and provide challenging students specialised solutions.

7. Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Language Support: Teachers can help students who might have trouble understanding technical topics because of language hurdles by using NLP algorithms to provide language support. AI-driven applications can provide in-the-moment translations, clarifications, or condensed versions of content to aid comprehension.

8. Student Support and Mentoring: Artificial intelligence chatbots or virtual assistants can be used to offer students

round-the-clock support. They can provide resources, respond to commonly asked questions, and provide advice on technical matters to help students get through their technical education experience.

9. Predictive Analytics: AI systems can review student data to identify possible difficulties or subject areas in which students may struggle. In order to avoid learning gaps and foster student achievement, teachers can proactively intervene and offer focused help.

10. Collaborative Learning and Peer Assessment: AI can enhance peer evaluation and feedback in collaborative learning contexts. Students can use AI-based tools to evaluate projects, offer helpful critique, and participate in group problem-solving exercises.

Conclusion: It is crucial to remember While AI can be a great help to teachers in technical education, it should be understood as a tool to complement rather than replace their knowledge. AI should be employed to increase teachers' instructional capabilities and boost student outcomes because teachers play a crucial role in guiding and mentoring pupils.

RECENT TRENDS ABOUT EQUALITY IN EDUCATION

Dr. Ranjan Kishore Mallick¹, Dr. Umasankar Das^{2,*}, Asish Tripathy³, Bishnu Kalyan Ojha⁴

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Bhubaneswar, Odisha

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Abstract:

India has witnessed tremendous learning needs. Innovative learning models include online and blended learning; high - access, technology - rich learning environments; and personalized learning models. Preparing All Students for College and 21st development in educating and training its vast human resource of over one billion through sustained effort of conventional and distance mode of education. In pursuit of making Right to Education a reality, the Government has been initiating efforts for developing the educational infrastructure and training human capital. Consequently, the Country with a literacy rate of 64.84%, at higher education level, 13578 colleges and 407 universities along with 106 distance education institutions address needs of 11.7 million students. These institutions of learning, in true sense have been instrumental in educating the vast human resource of over one billion but democratization of education i.e. access and equity to education is still a dream to be realized. Trends in education are always appearing, such as i-Pads and online testing, but with recent developments in national standards and a new federal emphasis on equity, the 2013-14 annual academic year will have a set of trends all its own. Important strategies is necessary to achieve our nation's education goals if we are serious about preparing all students for citizenship, work, and life in our increasingly global world: Building a 21st Century Infrastructure- Building the 21st century education environment for equity, innovation, and improvement requires a technology infrastructure.

Keywords: Equality, Education

1. Introduction:

Education has been the main instrument of human development and its importance has been emphasized through fundamental rights, principles, statutes / acts in a number of countries. At the international

level, attempts have been made at various congregations to focus on aspects of education as a part of fundamental human right. According to Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations 1948):

1. Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.

2. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall

a) expand and improve comprehensive early childhood care and education, especially for the most vulnerable and disadvantaged children.

b) ensure that by 2015 all children, particularly girls, children in difficult circumstances and those belonging to ethnic minorities, have access to and complete free and compulsory primary education of good quality.

c) ensure that the learning needs of all young people and adults are met through equitable access to appropriate learning and life- skills programmes.

d) achieve a 50% improvement in levels of adult literacy by 2015, especially for women, and equitable access to basic and continuing education for all adults.

e) eliminate gender disparities in primary and secondary education by 2005, and achieve gender equality in education by 2015, with a focus on ensuring girls' full and equal access to and achievement in basic education of good quality; and improve all aspects of the quality of education and ensure excellence of all so

promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all Nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace.

Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children. Similarly, at World Education Forum Dakar, Senegal, April 2000, the framework for action was developed according to which goals for international communities were defined and these are that recognized and measurable learning outcomes are achieved by all, especially in literacy, numeracy and essential life skills.

The Dakar Framework identified education as a human right and affirmed that no country seriously committed to Education for All would be thwarted in their achievement of this goal by lack of resources. The Framework's goals and objectives have been adopted by countries and donor institutions around the world.

2. Equality of Education in India:

In India, education has been accorded prime importance and thus it has found place in Fundamental Rights (Part III) and Directive Principles of State Policy (Part IV) of the Constitution of India. The Constitution of India has given certain rights to the citizens of India which are better known as the Fundamental Rights (Article 12 to 35). According to Article 21A —Right to Education in Right to Freedom (Article 19 to 22), the State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of six to fourteen years in such manner as the State may, by law, determine. Along with the

Fundamental Rights there are also the Directive Principles of State Policy (Article 36 to 51) which are fundamental governing principles of the country and it is the duty of the State to apply these Directive Principles for making the laws.

According to Article 45 of the Constitution of India, the State has to make provision for free and compulsory education for children within a period of ten years from the commencement of the Constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years. However, a particular Act to this effect did not exist so the Government of India took initiative of framing Right to Education Act. The Constitution (86th Amendment) Act, 2002, enacted in December 2002 seeks to make free and compulsory education a Fundamental Right for all children in the age-group 6-14 years by inserting a new Article 21-A in Part III (—Fundamental Right) of the Constitution.

3. Trends and Technology in Education:

Technology in college is taking a lesson from the enterprise model long practiced in business. The education space is abuzz with three major technology trends that are changing the landscape. Traditional publishers will need to re-think their offering, as printed educational materials may soon be a thing of the past. Early childhood education through online & mobile learning: There's no arguing that children love tablets. Adoption is very high by school boards and parents have been using them with their children at home as well. This truly makes learning fun for

students and increases overall engagement. Exciting examples include niche products like LocoMotive Labs, for children with special needs, and Motion Math, for learning math through fun games.

Free and open education: Services like CK-12, Coursera, Khan Academy, Udemy and the Massive Open Online Courses feature rich content and free, open education for all. CK-12 is one of the most disruptive companies highlighted at Launch. The content is rich, interactive, customizable and very high quality. CK-12 is hardly alone as this trend is growing – Coursera is another big player in combining education with technology. During a fireside chat with Jason Calacanis, founder of LAUNCH, Coursera's co-founder Daphne Koller highlighted how Coursera uses data and analytics to track everything on the Coursera platform to continue to improve the experience and understand how humans learn. Koller discussed overall adoption, clarified some misconceptions about completion rates, and provided insights into the university partnerships and the overall growth of Coursera.

Workbooks are now Tablets: Complementing the first two trends is the rise in tablet-based education inside and outside the classroom. According to this Google infographic, 70% of college students planned to purchase an e-textbook in 2013. Complementing that trend, Open Colleges produced research showing that 80% of teachers think tablets can improve classroom learning. With this type of demand from both sides of the desk, there's good reason for companies like Amplify to believe that the classroom of the future will

be tablet-based.

4. Emerging trends in Online Education:

The rise of online education has been meteoric in recent years, spurred on by advances in Internet services, software, and public perceptions toward collaborative learning. Here are ten trends in online education that are currently materializing in the field that we can expect to continue onward into the near future:

1. A shift to open source—Learning Management Systems (LMS) have traditionally been paid services. Newer open source systems like Open Class are free and open source and have received a warm welcome from both students and educators.
2. Being considered more valuable by employers—Online educational degrees have up until now been largely regarded as not as valuable on the job market as traditional degrees. As the number online students reaches critical mass this perception will change.
3. Hybrid courses are surfacing—Blended classes that feature some online education and some face to face teacher interaction have become popular at some colleges in Miami and in other spots in the nation as well. These types of schools give students more options.

4. Enrollment growing exponentially compared

to brick-mortar-schools— online education enrollment as a 21% growth rate compared to the paltry 2% growth rate in overall higher education. This trend can be expected to continue as the technological services become easier to distribute.

5. Shared data, collaborative functionality— what will facilitate the easier distribution will be shared texts and the ability to collaborate on projects remotely. In-person learning will no longer be seen as superior to distance learning
6. Shift from books and closed texts to digital content distribution—Textbooks are slowly being phased out in deference to digital content distribution systems that allow people to access texts and learning materials online through variety of mobile devices.
7. Social learning systems to be cloud-based— these digital content distribution systems will be social and cloud-based. Open Class, for instance, allows enrolled students to share data and collaborate remotely through cloud services that do not have extensive hardware requirements.
8. Podcasting is on the rise—nearly half of US teens and adults have listened to a podcast and this number will grow. Podcasting will continue to be adopted more as an educational tool.
9. Better technology is emerging—there was a time when online education consisted of reading textbooks online. These days students have a wide variety of tools at their disposal, including text chat, immersive multimedia, virtual classrooms, and digital whiteboards. These tools will be further streamlined by better cloud services.

10. Social media is becoming educational—social media, which has long been viewed as the opiate of the masses, is more and more being utilized to facilitate social learning tools and Learning Management Systems. Expect entire educational social media networks to build off of sites like Facebook. Many of these trends are already surfacing in big ways in the educational industry, others are still embryonic. The rise of online education is expected to continue and many of these issues will play big roles in how perceptions of e-learning change in society.

5. Reason behind disparity in students' outcome:

Understanding why students outcomes vary so dramatically along race and class lines in America is central to formulating effective education policy interventions. Disagreements about how to improve schooling outcomes for poor students stem in part from different beliefs about the problems that underlie the unsatisfactory outcomes in many of our nation's public College. Broadly speaking, critics tend to invoke, at least implicitly, one of the following explanations for why students in high-poverty College are not performing as well as we would like:

1. Colleges serving poor and minority students have fewer resources than they need. In this case, a potential solution would be to provide more money to disadvantaged College.
2. High-poverty College lacks the capacity to substantially improve student learning, independent of financial resources. Potential solutions to this problem would involve helping College improve the quality of their

standard operating practices, or increasing the instructional capacity of staff in these Colleges through professional development or more selective hiring.

3. High-poverty College does not have sufficient incentives or flexibility to improve instruction. Proponents of this perspective argue that without clarifying key objectives and holding key actors accountable, additional spending will be squandered.

4. College matter only so much. The real problem rests with the social context in which College operates namely, the family, neighborhood, and peer environments that under this perspective make it difficult for low-income students to take advantage of educational opportunities. Adopting accountability or market oriented reforms without changing social policy more broadly will punish educators for factors beyond their control, and potentially drive the most able teachers toward College serving less-disadvantaged students.

For some reason, current education policy debates often seem to be argued as if the problems listed above are mutually exclusive. In contrast, we believe that there is likely some truth to each of these major explanations; College confronts no single problem that can be addressed with just one solution. Identifying the optimal policy response to the mix of problems that plagues our public College is complicated by the possibility that these problems might interact with each other. For example, it may be the case that certain curriculum reforms are effective only if they are accompanied by an increase in resources such as student support services, or by an increase in teacher

quality generated by reforms to hiring and tenure policies. Social science theory and common sense are likely to carry us only so far in identifying the most effective—and cost-effective—mix of education policy changes. For almost every education intervention that some theory suggests might be effective, another plausible theory suggests that the intervention is likely to be ineffective or even harmful. Education policy also needs to be guided by rigorous evaluation evidence about what actually works in practice.

6. Conclusion:

Although significant progress has been made in India towards enhancing literacy in the country and universalization of basic education, but there still remains a lot to be accomplished in order to achieve the mission of 100% literacy along with increasing the enrolment of children in the schools and motivating them to complete the schooling, thus reducing the drop out ratio at various stages. Greater dependence on technology in education audio-visual aids for teaching purpose so as to encourage learning by doing and supplement face-to-face with audio-visual teaching will surely help in increasing the literacy rate and improving the involvement of students in education. Schools and Colleges should take initiatives to improve the quality of the education delivered to the students. Providing tablet PC's and a Wi-Fi enabled campus, enables the students to gain uninterrupted access to knowledge. Shyness may be one of the reasons for students to avoid to interact in a classroom. To overcome this, Webinars on a particular topic for students having doubts in that topic

can be conducted frequently as a doubt clearing session. Equality in education can be achieved by avoiding the categorization of students based on castes and communities. Mark based system helps in improving the equality among the students. Parents below poverty line should be encouraged by the Government, to send their son/daughter to schools or colleges, by providing scholarships for them.

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ROLE OF PROFESSIONALS IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract:

Nation building may be defined as the process through which the boundaries of the modern states and those of the national community become congruent. Our Professionals are the future of India. They are responsible for a country's name and fame. If the power of young men or students is channeled towards positive objectives, the entire nation will progress in all directions. With the birth of freedom, this obligation has grown enormously. "Give me the children, and I will change the nation," one famous educator has properly declared. Only with the cooperation of all its residents can a nation accomplish progress.

Keywords: Nation building, Professionals, Educator, Progress

1. Introduction:

Our Professionals are the future of India. They are responsible for a country's name and fame. If the power of young men or students is channeled towards positive objectives, the entire nation will progress in all directions. With the birth of freedom, this obligation has grown enormously. "Give me the children, and I will change the nation," one famous educator has properly declared. Only with the cooperation of all its residents can a nation accomplish progress. As a result, it is critical that students understand their responsibilities. India is a growing nation. Young guys can contribute significantly to development work. They may travel to the countryside for adult education, social outreach to the destitute villagers, or other purposes. The young men may do a lot in the development work. They may go to the villages for adult education, for doing social service to the poor villagers,

for teaching new technology in farming and other such vocations. The trained and learned young men may bring about green revolution in the country. They may preach ideas of secularism in the country. By leading an ideal simple life they may lead literate. In emergencies, they may do a lot in controlling floods etc. we can mobilize student power to preach communal harmony. In brief, the student power may be used at every moment whenever the nation needs their services.

2. Role of professionals:

To play their role properly in modern India we should teach the youth of our country to make themselves disciplined. They should not be led away by the anti- national forces. They should not go astray in their schools and colleges. In all, the teachers and professor may fill the students' hearts with idealism. The young men should learn

lessons of hard work, high morality, books as may create such ideals. Mahatma Gandhi and Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru lived simple life. They fought and brought freedom to the country. They believed in ideal life of a true patriot. Let us (the students), learn lessons of patriotism and sacrifice from the life of Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, Shri Lal Bahadur Shastri and Rafi Ahmed Kidwai. The students should live for the nation and follow the road paved by our beloved Nation builder, Sardar Vallabh Bhai Patel. The educational institutions should frame courses and syllabi conforming to these ideals. Mere preaching and teaching is incomplete and insufficient. The teaching must have some objective. The teaching should make the students enable to shoulder the responsibility of national reconstruction. By inspiring high ideals among the masses the students can make the nation great.

The first duty of students is toward themselves. They should keep their bodies healthy and active. They should improve their health from the very beginning. A sound body has a sound mind. To keep themselves strong, they should take a keen interest in games and sports and different forms of physical exercises. A weak student can do nothing. He is unable to do anything for the good of his country or to himself. Students should give up bad habits like smoking, gambling and aimless wandering. These bad habits affect their health directly

or indirectly. The students must understand that they are students and should pay full attention to their studies. They should devote a greater part of their time to the pursuit of knowledge and wisdom. They should play for them to learn and to prepare themselves for future responsibilities in life. Without good education they will not be able to shoulder their future burdens.

3. Conclusion:

Knowledge without character is wickedness. Students should cultivate in them good manners and purity of life. They should not follow only intellectual knowledge, but also from their moral character. Obedience to parents, respect for teachers, and sympathy for the poor, love for all and malice towards none should be their chief moral ideals. They should be refined in their taste, sweet in their speech and polite in their behavior. In short, the duty of students is to prepare for future responsibility. He is to remove the evils such as child marriage, gambling, drinking, smoking, litigation, superstition, untouchability, illiteracy, adulteration, corruption and dowry system, from the society. They should create in them a spirit of social service. Students are the future rulers and leaders of our country. They are the reserve force of our country. They are the backbone of the country. The future of India depends on our students.

ENGINEERS: THE BACKBONE OF NATION

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Abstract:

Students will need to build the society, economy, and polity, which will meet the basic needs of the people, so that they are not driven by poverty, inequality, unemployment. Perhaps most importantly, it means the development of education. We are all students and still can make a difference to how things happen around us, by following the eminent trendsetters who have carved a niche for themselves and have collectively made a tremendous positive impact on nation building. The 2010 batch IAS officer, Armstrong Pame, popularly known as the 'Miracle Man' has built a 100 km long road famously known as the 'Peoples' Road' - connecting Manipur to Nagaland and Assam. He built the 'Peoples' Road' without any financial help from the government but from the funds offered by the general public and money raised through social media. He also went ahead and contributed his own salary for the cause.

Keywords: Engineers, Nation, Society, Civilization

1. Introduction:

In year 1968, Government of India has declared 15th September as "Engineers Day" as a tribute to the greatest Engineer BharatRatna Mokshagundam Vishveshvar aiya. Born on 15th September 1860, Dr. Vishveshvaraiya went to become India's most prolific civil engineer, dam & bridge builder, economist, statesman and can be counted among the last century's foremost nation-builders. Nation as well as society recalls the priceless and irreplaceable contribution of their engineers in nation building.

The history of engineers is as old as civilisation. As civilisation developed

people began reshaping their environment with villages, farms, watersheds, roads, ships and eventually towns. With each advancement came new challenges that required more complex and creative solutions, which were solved by experiments as well as experience. With the passage of time, there has been considerable overhauling in the system. The advent of computer & software has completely changed the scenario in infrastructure sector. Quality in construction, planning, scheduling, organising, co-ordinating, controlling, management etc has been improved and elapsed time minimised.

2. Important role for professional

In religious scripture, Bhagwan Vishwakarma has been enshrined as an engineer & architect of the Devlok. In Treta Yug, during departure of Shri Ram to Sri Lanka, two warriors of the Vanar Sena – Nal and Neel have showed their engineering expertise by constructing stone bridge “Shri Ram Setu” across the ocean between present day Dhanushkodi in Rameshwaram (Bharat) & Mannar (Sri Lanka). The bridge, having approximately 30-35 Km length & 3 Km width, is the unique model of ancient engineering dexterity.

Engineers play a very important role in every walk of life. They are technically skilled professionals, who are responsible for solving problems through the use of machines, devices, systems, materials and processes. They convert knowledge of basic sciences into products. Their main focus is on making things work efficiently and effectively by applying the theories and principles of sciences and mathematics to research, and develop economic solutions to technical problems. The engineer differs from scientist by the nature of their training. While the scientists try to explore the natural world and discover new knowledge about the universe and how it works, engineers apply that knowledge to solve real problems, often with an eye toward improving cost and efficiency.

Their works are the link between the perceived social needs and economic applications. They are the bridge between science and art. Engineers are the backbone of nation building and the purpose of engineering is to innovate, design, create

and maintain products, system and equipment for the benefit and wellbeing of humans. They help improve living conditions for the common people. If a country fails to realise the role of engineers in her nation building and the engineers are leaving for better opportunities abroad, then the country will continue to experience collapsed buildings and bridges, substandard products, failed roads, communication failures, environmental hazards, epileptic power supply etc. Engineers contribute to the nation’s technological & industrial progress. As nations in the world are undergoing reformation and the economy is getting more modernised, consumption patterns have expanded and demand is constantly on the increase. There is therefore a growing consciousness of quality control at every level of production.

The engineers have to realise their responsibility and play an effective role in tackling today’s complex issues in the nation building. To build a nation is to make it habitable for the citizens by providing social amenities, infrastructural facilities, job creation and security and many more; the engineers therefore have a very important role to play. Thus, they are duty bound to design products, machineries and plants to manufacture these products, and systems to ensure quality and efficiency. They are to design, plan and supervise construction of buildings, and ensure their safety and stability against hazards; design highways, bridges, railways and transit systems, dams, irrigation canals, power systems, ports, harbours as well as off-shore structures. Engineers should equally know that it is their duty to develop and implement

improved ways to extract, process and use raw materials; develop new raw materials that can improve product performance and take advantage of advances in technology to harness the power of the sun, the gas, the earth, atoms and electricity to supply the nation's power needs; analyse the impact of the products they develop or systems they design on the environment and the people; design ways of managing the nation's waste, converting or recycling them to useful products. Parts of their functions also include determining the cause of component failures, estimating the time and cost of completing new projects as well as maintaining the existing ones. Engineers are pivotal not only in infrastructure, but can act a catalyst in the field of trade and commerce too. In sales and management, an engineering background enables one to discuss the technical aspects of projects/products and assist in the planning,

installation and product use. With such a vast and varied nature of their job, the engineers are really the foundation stone of a nation's building and their role cannot be neglected in a nation's all round progress. The engineers on their part should be proud of what they do and contribute effectively towards the growth of their country and the world at large.

3. Conclusion

The engineers have to realise their responsibility and play an effective role in tackling today's complex issues in the nation building. To build a nation is to make it habitable for the citizens by providing social amenities, infrastructural facilities, job creation and security and many more; the engineers therefore have a very important role to play. Thus, they are duty bound to design products, machineries and plants to manufacture these products, and systems to ensure quality and efficiency.

NEED FOR PROFESSIONAL ETHICS AND ETHICAL VALUES IN THE TEACHING PROFESSION: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract:

Today Ethics is one of the most concerning issues. The moral value of people is gradually degrading with passage of time and development of society. In order to fulfill their personal requirements people are ready to indulge themselves in any kinds of unethical practices. Although ethical and moral character of a child is largely influenced by his or her family but the teacher's role cannot be denied. A teacher can raise the morality of a student by encouraging the ethical practices which help them to develop an in depth knowledge and awareness of their own and other cultures. In this paper an attempt has been made to focus on the concept of ethics and its relation with the teaching profession and finally a code of ethics for teachers in professional education has been recommended.

Keywords: -Ethics, Unethical Practices, Morality, Code of Ethics.

1.Introduction:

The word ethics has been derived from Greek word 'ethikos' which means ones moral character. Ethics is a part of Philosophy which deals with systemizing, defending and recommending the concept of right and wrong conduct. It helps the people to understand what is wrong and what is right. If anyone has proper knowledge of good and bad then they could control his or her activity within the moral boundary. Ethics is universally accepted. It is applicable everywhere whether incase of personnel life, professional life, business trade and commerce. Ethical behavior is the way a living creature acts and their behavior explains about their morality. The tradition education system was different from the

modern system as in traditional education more emphasis was given mainly to the educational values while in modern education these values does not find any place. At present educational institutions are now transformed into a commercial business houses which has been established for earning profit not for value enrichment in the field of education. People are also ready to pay any amount in order to get better education for their siblings. Teaching is a noble profession where teachers provide selfless service to the people of society so that students could enhance their knowledge, ability and establish themselves in life but due to commercialization of education system ethical values are not getting much importance in these commercial educational

organizations as main objective of these organization is to earn profit not enrich values. People who are directly or indirectly engaged in teaching profession should have to maintain high standard of professional ethics or high moral value in order to discharge his or her duties and responsibility properly. They have to set an example in society by discharging his duty honestly in any adverse condition so that people of society could trust them and student could want be like him.

Professional ethics is need of present time as many educational institutions are not getting teacher having proper knowledge of professional ethics. Now as days despite of having all kinds of educational degrees, extra qualifications, subject knowledge, professional ethics are not found in the people who wanted to be teacher. Since teaching is not just about sharing knowledge of subject-matter with the students, it is just beyond that. Teacher plays a significant role not only in educating the people society but also give stress in bringing out the potentialities form the learners and nurture it accordingly and provide new talent to the society. Teaching is regarded as noble profession as it contributes in nation building by creating good quality human resources, responsible citizens, socialized individual and creative personality. Human resource is the best resource of any nation as it has capability to develop a great nation by their creativity and endless efforts. India is the only nation where more than 65 per cent of total population is of below the age of 35, which mean India is the country of young people and it has potential to become super power. Igniting the mind of young people

and guiding them to the right direction is the responsibility of the teachers'. Hence this profession requires a lot of commitment, dedication and sincerity towards their institution and learners. So, if they do not have the knowledge of profession ethics, it will become a barrier in the development of institution, education system, learners, society and nation as a whole and ultimately it will affects the overall performance of the student as well as nation.

The profession code of ethics provides some framework of guidelines so that a professional could conduct their work with commitment, full dedication, sincerity, honesty with integrity. A professional has to perform their duty as per the ethical code of conduct to get best result otherwise problem may arise in achievement of core objective of the profession. The professional ethics deal with principles, values that professional implemented to create a conducive atmosphere in the workplace. Professional knowledge and skills is a key element of success that every profession should acquire to do their services with determination and full commitment. Every professional has certain aim and objectives and in order to achieve those objective the professional apply those acquired code of professional ethics. Professional code of ethics helps a professional to complete their work very easily without any obstacle.

The professional code of ethics that has been developed for the teachers are purposely protects the rights of students. It becomes very important for the teachers to understand their work ethics and values before entering in teaching profession. As a teacher, they

have huge role to play in the entire teaching learning process. They should be active in educational process and encourage and reinforce the students be converted into active learner by using different strategies and techniques. It is also important for the teachers to understand the individual differences, intellectual level, interest and attitudes of the learner so that teaching could be done as per their level of understanding. Also they could put more emphasis on providing freedom to the student so that they could express their problems without any hesitation and fear. The professional code of ethics play most important role in developing personality and behavior of the teachers. If teachers apply all those code of ethics in the teaching profession, undoubtedly it will develop the educational institutions, society, community and nation as a whole.

2. Necessity of Professional ethics in teaching profession:

Educational institutions are considered as the temple of knowledge which play vital role in bringing development in the society by sharing knowledge among the people of society. The teachers are the key elements of the education system. Without them the whole education system cannot function properly and teaching and learning process hamper. The teachers' plays significant role

in the educational process and their selfless service they can bring desired changes in the behavior of the students. Students are the future of any nation and it the teacher who can guide their activities towards right direction. It is the teacher who understands the latent potential of a student and brings them out and makes them realize the inner strength and encourage them to achieve everything by their endless efforts. A teacher can fulfill all the aims and objectives by applying his ability, teaching aptitude, content knowledge, pedagogy and most important professional ethics. Some important people already states that the teachers should be unbiased while teaching and evaluating students. Buber (1970) suggests that teacher –student relationships ought to be characterized by a principle of reciprocity. Since, communication is the key element in the teaching learning process. Teachers must put emphasis on creating respectful relationship with students.

In absence of professional ethics in teaching profession severe problem may arise and that become an obstacle on way development of students. Teachers act role model, source of inspiration, and act as motivator students. They have the capability to develop leadership quality among the students. In most of the cases it has been found that student always wanted to be like their favorite teacher and for that they try to follow the footprints left by their favorite teachers. A teacher must have good behavior and positive attitude towards everything related to their profession and students. One of the important roles of teacher is to solve real life problems, issues and barriers of the students that come across

during the teaching learning process. It has been already mentioned earlier that a teacher should proper knowledge of professional ethics. If they fails to understand and implement it, then they might not be satisfied with their profession and thus, it will hamper the performance of the students. In order to continue this development process society needs well-trained teachers.

The teachers must follow code of profession ethics and values to discharge their duty and responsibility successfully.

Important code of professional ethics needed for a teacher to conducting teaching and learning process more efficiently and effectively.

- A teacher should always keep themselves update as per the need of present environment.
- A teacher should have ability to adapt themselves in any environment.
- The teacher should always be honest towards his or her profession.
- The teacher should be unbiased in any situation especially during the evaluation of progress of the students.
- The teacher should respect all students equally irrespective of their cast, creed, religion, socio economy status, gender, and colour.
- The teacher should try to develop a good respectful relationship with the students so student can easily trust their teacher and share their problem without any hesitation.
- Teacher should communicate with care and affection with the students.
- Teacher must act wisely in all kind of

adverse situation.

- Teacher should always keep themselves away from any kinds of conflicts and controversial issues.
- Teacher should always keep it in his or her mind that he or she has to set an example and so act accordingly.
- The vision and mission of the teachers should be clear in all respect so that they could control their activity towards achievement their goal.
- A teacher should provide all kinds of opportunity to students to excel in all aspects.
- A teacher should always remain active in teaching and learning process.

3. Conclusion:

It is the duty and responsibility of teachers at all level that they should put emphasis on imparting quality education to each section of the society irrespective of their cast, class, religion. Most importantly the main duty of a teacher is to bring optimum development in each and every section of the society without any biasness towards a particular cast, group, class, or religion. Teacher should have equal respect for all group of society. Teachers should try to develop professional ethics within them so that they could perform their duty very honestly. The teachers should take the responsibility in his shoulder to take the teaching profession to the highest peak by performing their duty very efficiently and their endless efforts. Therefore, for successful teaching, the knowledge of professional ethics and its implementation is very essential for teachers.

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ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF STUDENTS IN NATIONAL BUILDING

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Abstract:

The role of students is very vital in respect to nation building. They are the key players of the society. They may play their role globally. They may contribute in any ways. Students must maintain their dignity by holding the arms of discipline. They must have their eyes on their aim. They may create ideals by virtue of their sincere efforts not only in the institution but also to the society.

Keywords: Students, National Building

1. Introduction:

Students, the future of a nation, play a very vital role in nation building. Every individual countryman can play its role in nation building by doing his duties in right manner. One should be sincere about his duties not only for self but also in the prospects of the nation. As we all know that our life is very short and we have a lot to do for our society, our nation and for the whole world. Mainly two duties are there which we have to play sincerely. One is to do the maximum efforts in the shortest possible duration without taking stress and secondly is whatever we may be in the society; we have to do our work with sincere efforts.

As we know that the future of country or of a nation fully depends upon its citizens so there is a great need of healthy minds. This is possible only when the discipline is inculcated by making the students aware of

their duties and responsibilities. For making young generation an integral part of nation building, the seeds of discipline must be sown in their minds through moral values. Whatever knowledge is being acquired by the student's that should be utilized for the betterment of self, society and the nation. Student's prime duty is towards their teachers and parents. The education system must stress on the all round development of the students.

Students may contribute towards the society and the nation by keeping good deeds and moral conduct. The educational values should help them to mould themselves into dutiful citizens. As we all know that academic discipline deserves serious consideration. Students should not mislead their self by indulging in the activities which may take them away from their destination. Students must be cautious and sincere about

their future. They should know their role in the society. Mainly students deal with study, as duty. This very duty of process of learning brings knowledge and off course social and cultural, traditional touch amongst them. This very tradition and culture remain in their heart till they get older and become a sincere part of the nation and society. Student's life gives a lot the children by virtue of taking part in co-curricular activities and many other activities. These very habits help children to inculcate patriotic touch amongst them. Maintaining the dignity of student's life brings a lot in them. Students can play their role by following means:-

As professionals, employee of an institution, a part of NGO's, counselors, sincere politician, an integral part of defense department, a scientist, policy maker, a true citizen, a businessmen, economist, a writer, a teacher, an administrative, an eminent personality, social worker, a farmer, a motivator, a guider, a preacher to guide society, great saints, social reformer, sincere parents, path maker, followers creator, great educationist and many more

2. Knowing-part:

Nature is the mother of all living organism. The Earth gives platform to nature.

Nation: is the Environment or Nature comprised of, five elements namely water, land, oxygen, sky, air and many more resources. The oldest and highest biological transformation made human to be born. The Nature gives platform to nation.

Our mother Nation: Group of humans survived together by sharing the natural resources framed ownership towards Natural

Resources. They have common rules and principles to be followed for protecting and preserving both nature, and humans for their wellbeing and living. So, Humans are the son/daughter of our mother nation.

Learning-part:

Over a period of 5000 years, the whole world witness many humans fighting and ruling and controlling one over the other. The time line history provides evidences for the same. Our ancient Indians lived with enormous blessing, wealth, health, peace and happiness. Our scriptures give such information. How Our India is formed can be learnt from such scripts?

Mind mapping Part: Every student as a future citizen of our nation should mind map how and by whom these nation is still living and existing. This makes them to realize the roles performed by our ancients to preserve our nation. They can follow their ancient people's methodology like unity in diversity, fortitude, forbearance, Sacrifice, sava, service, dharma, karma, moksha so on so forth

Conclusion:

By observing the whole contents of the topic, we may conclude that the role of students is very vital in respect to nation building. They are the key players of the society. They may play their role globally. They may contribute in any ways. Students must maintain their dignity by holding the arms of discipline. They must have their eyes on their aim. They may create ideals by virtue of their sincere efforts not only in the institution but also to the society.

HUMAN RESOURCES TRAINING SYSTEM UPDATES INPRE UNIVERSITARY INSTITUTE

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Abstract:

Through studies and research carried out in the framework of this paper, an attempt was made to highlight the need for professionalization of teaching activity, starting from the current situation and where we want to go. For starters I made a parallel between profession-like theoretical object unlike profession-as the object of everyday practice. Considering the fact that the teaching profession has an extremely powerful human dimension, involving not only knowledge and skills but also attitudes, values, ethos, in a word, a professional conscience I approached the size of the teaching profession and the training system. The current and future training of teaching staff in Romania following the Directorates-General of the European Union are considering the importance of professionalization of a career in teaching, in which teachers continuous training is regulated and mandatory. In this context, we deemed it necessity to introduce the competencies required for the teaching profession, as well as the acquisition of additional skills such as: computer-assisted teaching, teaching in foreign language, educational counseling and career orientation, adult education, etc. Finally, we presented our conclusions and proposals.

Keywords: Profession, competence, job, expert teacher, human dimension

1. Introduction:

We are in front of the description of the identity of teaching profession as effort of building the profession different from the “job” (known as daily practice). If “job” is the result of an intuitive and imitative assimilation, without knowledge, “profession” means knowledge and structured competences in a professional model. From this perspective there are a lot of persons who think that teaching activity means “job”.

Between the aspects that are appearing in answering with clarity at this questions are some prejudices that Cl.

Gautier and collaborators (1999) are remembering. One of the most common prejudices is the one that says that being teacher represents: knowing the teaching subject, having talent, intuition and culture, having experience. Therefore, according to this prejudice, every person who known a teaching subject, has talent and intuition and experience can be a teacher and maybe one that has success. It is obvious that this point of view leads at a lack of the necessity of professionals in the teaching area. There are lot of opinions regarding the teaching activity as far as this has the competences of being a profession: some of them are real obstacles in defining the model of teaching

profession, some suggests new approaches for the model of teaching profession which try to not limit the model only at professional standards.

2. The dimension of teaching:

The effort of legitimize the teaching profession in the field of social activities and professions must consider that the teaching profession has a extremely powerful human dimension that implies not only knowledge and competences (described as professional standards) but also attitudes, values, time, in one word a professional consciousness (hard to standardize).

It is known that a teacher, an educator, works in a space with lots of areas of incertitude, space that is characterized by the simultaneous existence of two types of situations:

1. Repetitive situations, predictable for which the teacher has the answers from his professional stock, from his competences needed to approach and solve in due time and with efficiency;
2. Unexpected teaching situations, unusual, creative that demands new solutions and for which the teacher doesn't have (or has only partly) the competences needed for approaching and solving them rapidly. This type of situations demands innovation, creativity, therefore the dimension of attitudinal intervention, and sometimes "artistic".

Regarding the dilemma of professionalizing the teaching activity, the European Union has its own answer that it is also an answer for the countries members of the Union. In Brussels, in June 2005, the

European Commission organized a conference where, at the end of it, it was adopted the document: Common European Principles for Teacher Competences and Qualifications. The main message was the teaching career's professionalization that regards countries like Romania, purposes regarding this are: teaching career's professionalization, resizing the rapport between theoretical and practical part of the curriculum in teacher's preparation, "an educational market of continuous formation's programs" development based on a free competition system by which teachers benefits of a diversified offer from continuous formation providers. Regarding the professionalization of the teaching activity phenomenon, the specialists in educational sciences from Romania are expressing points of view, prof. Emil Păun claims that it is a "formation process of capacities and competences' set in a field based on assimilating a knowledge system (theoretical and practical), process lead deductively by a relative profession's model". In prof. Mirela Costandache's vision professionalization is: "a rationalization process of scientific and psycho-pedagogical knowledge and efficient practices' activation in educational situation". In the theory of professionalization that takes shape, methodological knowledge have priority whose objectives are "knowing to do", "learning new behaviours". This efforts are aiming to train "the professional" with skills wherewith can apply what they have learned in practical situations similar with educational practice. Legitimizing teaching profession involves two types of

approaches: inductive manner, exemplified by Cl. Gautier (1997). It is about building teacher's model in an inductive manner, starting with teacher's activity with success and performances towards generalizations. It is usually considered to be a manner based on the profession's specific and close to the complexity of everyday practice, a deductive manner, based on building standards and professional skills; a valuable approach by establishing clear benches, but which are deemed to ignore the complexity of teacher and students and students' classes activities. The complexity of teaching activity, characterized by standards and competences on the one hand, and by a very specific human, on the other hand, requires, in prof. Th. Pălășan view, a dual approach to the problem of the teaching profession: descriptive: refer to teacher's functions, teacher's prestige, advantages and limitations of the profession; normative: refer to "what should the teacher be".

This duality leads eventually to a combination of this two approaches, which creates a new concept of "open professionalism" whose content is submitted by the same teacher as required by "the need that the teacher puts into practice the educational policy which is in a rapid evolution, which solicit him very much because it should be opened to circumstances, to progresses of research, to teamwork with colleagues, to school managers, to local administration, to parents, and at the same time, must be respected as a representative of a professional field".

3. The system of continuous training-tradition and present:

The need for professionalization is imperative in a context in which professionalization is a condition for improving teachers' status. This allows: identifying types of training for competences and standards needed for evaluating the evolution in teaching career.

Implementation of initial training and continuous training with the profession's demands imposed by the social and institutional evolutions but also by knowledge developments such as the rapid rhythm - which requires interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches or cross specializations that involves an ample training with multiple openings. "Romania is one of the 11 EU countries where teachers' continuous training is regulated and mandatory." Current and future systems of teachers' continuous training from Romania are following the EU general standards that consider the importance of teachers' career professionalization.

European principles are guiding public policy of the Member States of the European Union in the field of continuous education of teachers. We note in this context some of the common European principles aimed at the professionalization of teaching career: orientation towards quality standards in the field of initial training by higher education institutions; placement in the European context of continuous professional development / learning and lifelong training; orientation toward mobility in lifelong learning; reliance on partnerships in the plan of interscholastic relations and also in the plan of trans-scholastic relations (economic agents, suppliers of continuous education).

4. The legal regulation of the teachers' system of continuous training:

Teachers' training is currently conducted in Romania in accordance with Education Law no. 1/2011, accompanied by a group of regulatory documents such as "Methodology concerning the teachers' continuous training in secondary education", "Methodology concerning the organization and conduction of national examination for becoming definitive in the educational system" etc.

The "European Common Principles for forming teachers' competences and qualifications" is considering also the description of competences rated as "key competences", along with recognition of the place and role played by teachers, the teachers in the future European society of knowledge and is considering the preparation of students to become future citizens of the united Europe. The materialization of principles requires from teachers to be professionalized, oriented towards continuous development and self reflexivity in terms of educational competences that are appropriately remunerated. In the opinion of prof. R. Iucu, key competences that are going to be formed and developed by teachers should be: "teachers must be able: to work with information, technology and knowledge, to work with people in rural educational immediate environment: students, colleagues, educational scholar and non-scholar partners, to work with and in society, at different levels of complexity and expression: local, regional, national, European and global / worldwide.

A research from 2005, before the introduction of the Bologna system, research applied across Eastern Europe, shows for Romania, referring to personal initial education, that most teachers considered that this was appropriate to start the teaching career, but noted the need for "more practical activities in initial training" (42.86%). Most of the respondents (33.12 %) considered that the initial training system should be changed completely; study programs should lead to the acquisition of all key competences for teachers (knowledge of the specialized subject, theoretical and practical pedagogical training). The respondents of the mentioned research have indicated aspects that should be improved: 23.38 % of them stated that the curricula should have put more emphasis on pedagogical training (teaching, learning, evaluation, pedagogical communication, etc.) 19.81 % of them signalled the need for practical training and improvement of the relationship between theory and practice; 13.64 % of them emphasized the need to grow the training in the specialization (content / themes / teaching competences of the subject/ subjects).

5. Areas of expertise required for performance of teaching Profession:

The current education law, the National Education Law no.1 /2011, defines in his end the terms used. Thus we find the following definition of "competence": "it is the proven ability to select, combine and use appropriately knowledge, skills and other acquisitions consisting of values and attitudes for successful resolution of certain categories of work or learning situations, and also for personal or professional

development in terms of effectiveness and efficiency.”

Professional skills (according to the National Education Law) are a unitary and dynamic system of knowledge and skills. Their content can be shaped through several descriptors for knowledge and skills. The most important descriptors expressing knowledge concern: the definition and use of technical terms, and the use of specific language; analysis, comparison, explanation and interpretation processes and theoretical and practical specific phenomena (logical, psychological, economic, sociological, philosophical, civic, etc.). The most important skills descriptors expressed concern: application, transfer and problem solving with respect to each social or trans-disciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary sciences in part; critical and constructive reflection; creativity and innovation.

Professional competences and quality standards that are considered for building a teaching career, concordantly with the National Education Law, no.1 / 2011, consider the following bench: specialization in psycho-pedagogical and methodological area, orientations for evolution in the teaching career through training system and obtaining the teaching degrees, acquiring of new competences through conversion programs for new specializations and /or occupation of teaching positions other than those employed based on the initial training.

Also special attention is given to the acquisition of complementary competences such as computer assisted teaching; teaching

in foreign languages; educational counselling and career guidance; adult education etc. In the National Education Law are also presented transversal competences needed for the teaching profession. These are the valuable and attitudinal purchases that are over a certain area /study program.

6. Conclusion:

An attempt is made to highlight the need for professionalization of teaching activity, starting from the current situation and where we want to go through studies and research carried out in the framework of this paper. Considering the fact that the teaching profession has an extremely powerful human dimension, involving not only knowledge and skills but also attitudes, values, ethos, in a word, a professional conscience I approached the size of the teaching profession and the training system. The current and future training of teaching staff in Romania following the Directorates-General of the European Union are considering the importance of professionalization of a career in teaching, in which teachers continuous training is regulated and mandatory. In this context, we deemed it necessary to introduce the competencies required for the teaching profession, as well as the acquisition of additional skills such as: computer-assisted teaching, teaching in foreign language, educational counseling and career orientation, adult education, etc.

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QUALITY IMPROVEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND IT'S SCOPE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

The new social realities, particularly the interplay between democratization of education; unprecedented developments in information and communication technologies; emergence of knowledge society and globalization greatly influences the educational process of all societies. In this context, quality of education assumes an added importance and becomes the primary concern of all the stakeholders in education. The modern society focuses on creating, sustaining and improving the quality of life. Therefore good higher education is that which optimally contributes to the betterment of quality of life. The time is changing very fast. Globalization, Liberalization and Privatization have shifted the focus of education on quality. The communiqué of the world conference on Higher Education 2009 States that “Quality criteria must reflect the overall objectives of higher education, notably the aim of cultivating in students critical and independent thought and the capacity of learning throughout life. They should encourage innovation and diversity. “The old order changes the yielding place to new”. Change is the law of nature. Nature always offers scope for improvement, betterment and enlargement challenges are the integral parts of growth and progress. Yet we have to search for the scope of improvement. In every walk of life there’s an immense scope and possibility to improve the quality in Higher Education.

Keywords: Quality, Challenges, issues, Parameters.

1. Introduction:

The dictionary meaning of quality is “degree of excellence “and superiority in kind”. Delmore and E. Shakher (2002) defined quality as the degree of excellence of entire educational experience. According to G. Harmann and V. Meek (2000) quality in the context of higher education can be defined as judgement about the level of good achievement and the value and worth of that achievement. Quality is an enigmatic

concept. It is perplexing to define and often difficult to measure. The idea of Quality of one person often conflicts to that of another person.

In ancient India, Quality in education has been depicted in terms of its impact. “Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaya”ie. that which liberates human beings from narrow bondages in Quality Education. Again it says “Vidya Vinayen Shobhate , i.e. Quality Education makes a scholar modest Quality in Education

was maintained by adopting measure like admission on the basis of leaning potential , subject selection based on individual talent , interest and ability, quality of higher Education can be improved considerably through extension and optimum use of audio-visual technology, computers and intent networks.

2. Approaches to quality: Quality management has four basic components:- Quality Planning, Quality Assurance, Quality Control, and Quality Improvement Quality management is that aspect of the overall management function that determines and implements the quality policy.

PARAMETERS OF QUALITY

3. Challenges of Quality in Higher Education:

The main problems and challenges of higher education at present in India as follows:

- Lack of flexibility in Higher Education.
- Low confidence level of students.
- Lack of strategic planning.
- Lack of advance teaching strategies,
- teaching methodologies and various

tools.

- Lack of qualitative and quantitative Infrastructure.
- Lack of research.
- Lack of cooperation among colleagues
- Big gap between the syllabus at senior secondary level and at UG degree level and in some cases there is repetition of course contents.
- Lack of Quality books.
- Orientation and refresher courses are not serving any purpose except a mandatory requirement for higher grades.
- Lack of Quality and quantity of Human Resource in Education sector
- Low Enrolments at Higher Education
- Low employability
- Lack of guidance and counseling
- Defective system of Examination and Evaluation procedure
- Target less and defective education
- Lack of proper leadership in educational administration
- Low level of teaching.
- Lack of proper academic facilities
- Problem of medium of Instruction.
- Lack of Job oriented courses- technical and professional.
- More concentration on theory than practical.
- Non-productive research being conducted.

- Lack of planning at institutional level
- Lagging quality of curriculum due to lack of enthusiasm in revision and development of new curriculum.

4. How to improve quality in higher education:

- 1) Leadership and commitment of top management plays a significant role in quality improvement.
- 2) Creating an environment for learning and staff development is crucial to do tasks right every time.
- 3) Adopt new philosophies and technologies.
- 4) Encourage new work and participatory management.
- 5) Develop a communication strategy to report progress and results.
- 6) Recognize the efforts of staff without creating a competitive environment.
- 7) Encourage quality circles and culture of quality (Mishra,2006).
- 8) Offers the opportunity of higher education to all these who have the potential to benefit.
- 9) Meets the developing needs of students for new modes of study and delivery of courses as well as leaving support.
- 10) Employs sufficient staff of the right caliber to achieve its missions and which recruits, develops, retains and rewards them adequately.
- 11) Syllabus of all subjects of all universities in state up to UG level be same and if possible there should be uniform syllabus at national level for UG

classes. The Joint Syllabus Designing Committee (JSDC) most consist of teacher's of high reputation from universities, colleges.

12) Without reading quality books one can not understand the true concept of a subject. Therefore Quality books plays a significant role in quality improvement.

13) Teachers Training Institute (TTI) can train the teachers about latest techniques of teaching. Power Point presentation, education through EDUSAT.

14) The Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) has more flexibility and meritorious student can earn more credit than others in a subject of his/her choice.

15) Each University should have its own Human Resource Evaluation Centre (HREC) so that examinations can be constructed at district level by State Govt.

5. Quality issues in higher education:

- a) Need Based and qualitative curriculum.
- b) Supervision and Monitoring.
- c) Research and Development.
- d) Qualitative Improvement of Teachers .
- e) Inculcation of values.
- f) Use of ICI
- g) Quality Academic Planning and support.
- h) Stimulation of Academic Environment.
- i) Quality Infrastructure.

6. Rater model for higher education:

RATER (Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy, and Responsiveness) model is

used to achieve quality in higher education. The figure below shows the RATER model for achieving quality in education. Parameters are-

- Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy

RATER Model for qualitative Higher Education

7. Conclusion:

In the present Scenario when the entire world is undergoing a very rapid change in Education specially in Higher Education, I am of the opinion that Education must have a cohesion with the growing demand of the mass. The Intellengtia and the Intellectual class should have a focus on the eradication of all the problems which hamper the growth,

cultivation, and encouragement of Quality in Higher Education. I thus, conclude that Education as a global issue requires a lot of fours on the means and measures for the improvement of quality. As a matter of fact, quality is of utmost importance in every sphere of life. Qualitative approach leads to quality. Keeping in view all the elements, factors, measures and principles I feel that the aforesaid techniques would effective and will beget beneficial effects to improvement of quality in Higher Education.

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CONCEPTUAL MODELLING OF PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS AS CHANGE AGENT IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract:

The professional education is an important pillar of nation building. The future leader should not only have right education but also progressive skills to uplift the nation from developing stage to developed one. But the present professional education in our country is lagging due to its static and regressive characteristics. This paper tries to address above mentioned problem with some innovative perspective and approach.

Keywords: Experiential Learning, Design Thinking, Engineering Excellence

1. Introduction:

The future of any country depends upon its students. A country's name and fame rest on the educated youth. In other words, the students are the real treasure of any country. If the power of young men or students is directed to constructive purposes, the whole nation will move to all round development. The biggest impact is made with professional education. Recent surveys conducted by various industrial body show that the large percentage of engineering students graduating from various educational institutes in India are not unemployable. The widening gap between industry standards and deteriorating quality of students' intake created huge turbulence in employment sector. If a comparison is made between American and Indian engineering education, the aspect that clearly distinguish the two systems is the teaching-learning process. While American system is more focused on skill based learning, in India it is still glued to knowledge based processes. But

unfortunately the students are not appreciating this approach due to lack of capacity and capability.

Most of the students are searching for shortcuts to certificate rather than toiling through volumes of text and reference books. Excellence in engineering is a distant dream. This lack lustre approach toward learning is indirectly hampering the national economy. If India to prosper in economic sector a growth rate of double digit is essential. Without excellence in engineering this is not possible to achieve.

To make the students take more interest in professional learning, the present practice of pedagogy needs paradigm shift. All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE), New Delhi, the apex planning and monitoring body of engineering education, has taken the timely step in this direction. The centre of education and training has shifted from teachers to students. What students can able to do after each subject, course or programme is the primary purpose

in outcome based education (OBE). One mechanism through which OBE can be implemented is experiential learning combined with design thinking.

2. Methodology:

Experiential Learning: Learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping experience and transforming it. “Experiential” means relating to or resulting from experience while “experimental” means relating to or based on experiment

Various studies show engineering excellence can be achieved through overall development in three domains, i.e., knowledge, skill and behavioural instincts. The cardinal dimensions to be looked into can be explained with the X, Y and Z axes.

X: Knowledge acquired by the engineer at any given stage and his/her ability to acquire more and re knowledge. The depth and width of these and the level of excellence reached constitute the measure for this dimension.

Y: Ability of the engineer to apply his/her knowledge for the progress and good of the society. The skills acquired, the productivity of application of the skills and knowledge to any given issue in service of the society constitute the measure for this dimension.

Z: Behavioural instincts and habits so that all actions of the engineer are within the framework of socially responsible conduct of affairs. Indian heritage is fortunately so rich in this, if these are put into real practice in all the day to day affairs excellence can automatically be reached.

In many engineering educational institutions the entire academic programme comprises of only undergraduate courses without any linkage with research, design, and industrial and engineering activities in practice. It is now well understood that an undergraduate education is better in an environment of post-graduate programme. Similarly, both the undergraduate and postgraduate programmes get better toned up when these are pursued in an industrial environment where engineering is practiced in the field or

Fig. 1: Basic dimensions of excellence in engineering

in a research environment such as those covered by doctoral and post-doctoral programmes; it would be even better if these postgraduate and research programmes are also pursued in an environment of applied research, design, consultancy, and field practices in industry or agricultural engineering. Engineering education will contribute significantly to the economy if all above three domains are given equal importance. The present situation also demands more and more emphasis on skill development so that employability issue is properly addressed.

Design Thinking: A human-centred innovation process that emphasizes observation, collaboration, fast learning, visualization of ideas, rapid concept prototyping, and concurrent business

analysis. It is a non-linear, iterative process that teams use to understand users, challenge assumptions, redefine problems and create innovative solutions to prototype and test. Involving five phases—Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test—it is most useful to tackle problems that are ill-defined or unknown.

Fig.2: Design thinking Process

The uniqueness of design thinking lies in the kinds of problems it addresses. When it comes to the problems to be solved with design thinking, we're not just talking about ordinary, common problems that have tried-and-tested solutions. We're talking about highly complex, "wicked" problems: the kind that refuse to be solved using standard methods and approaches. Not only are these problems difficult to define, but any attempt to solve them is likely to give way to even more problems. Wicked problems are everywhere, ranging from global issues such as climate change and poverty, to challenges that affect almost all businesses such as change management, achieving sustainable growth, or maintaining your competitive edge. Design thinking is an actionable approach which can be used to tackle the world's wickedest of problems. It fosters user-centricity, creativity, innovation, and out-of-the-box thinking. Engineering education in India is very similar to a wicked problem.

Combining design thinking with experiential learning will result in an education model

that is modular in architecture and is repeatable across different environment and context. Keeping the students at the centre of application all pedagogical approach will be more inclusive in nature. The learning behaviour of individual student will be mapped with compatible characteristics of other students. The collaborative groups will be formed among the fast, average and slow learners. The group learning will overcome the inertia of distractive learning. So each member in a group will remain in the main track of learning at different pace without losing the focus and purpose.

Conclusion:

Indian engineering education is now at a cross road. Through proper policies and perspectives she can join the developed world sooner through overall development in economic, social and political scenarios. Due to lack of interest for traditional knowledge based learning system by bulk of the student community, skill based learning should be implemented as quickly as possible. Experiential learning methodology based on design thinking principle will definitely yield result which will bring sea change in engineering education. More research work can be done to adapt various learning techniques to experiential teaching-learning system.

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ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY OF PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract:

Skill based education is instrumental in making remarkable contribution to nation development through creating proficient manpower, enhancing productivity, and improving quality of life. The main objective of professional education is to prepare individual for employment and business through skill and knowledge acquisition. In present scenario of science and technology, production of skilled and knowledgeable manpower according to the needs of society and industry is the need of hour. The rapid industrialisation of any country is due to acquisition of professional education. It gives systematic way of practical exposure to individual for producing goods and services which is necessary for development of any nation. This paper examined the benefits of professional educations, and its role in harnessing resources in nation's development.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Employable Skills, Professional Manpower, Sustainable Development

1. Introduction:

A nation should be developed by its people. People should work hard to strengthen it. As said by Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam "Nation development depends on what its people think". The development of a any country is depends on effective utilisation of human and physical resources which in turn, is depends on training of the manpower and skill development. Professional education is all about skills developments. Skilled workers which in turn increases productivity. Professional education enables people to acquire skills and knowledge which are needed in society and industry. Japan's rapid industrialisation is due to accumulation of technical skills, knowledge and it's strong commitment to education particularly training of engineers and skills. Professional education not only

improves analytical, functional abilities but it also enhance efficiency, skills, knowledge which is very much essential for economic development of any country.

2. Roles and Responsibility of Professional Students in Nation Building:

Skilled youth is the structural and functional framework of the nation. Every nation's pillar of success is its younger generation and its achievements. The future of the nation lies in the all-around development of students. Hence they play a supreme role in nation-building. There is a beautiful saying of Nelson Mandela that, "Youth of today are leaders of tomorrow" is true and applicable in each and every aspect. The educated students or more rightly we can say professional student's lays the foundation of development for any of the nations they are filled up with several

capabilities and potential of learning along with performing. They are filled up with mind, talents and creativity. Professional students can be from variety of sphere including, Education, Veterinary, Medicine, Law , Dentistry , Engineering, Business Administration, Nursing etc. If they raise their voice on any issue, they can bring the transformation. They are considered to be the voice of the nation. These students are like raw material or resources to the nation. The way they are shaped, they are likely to emerge in the same manner. The number of professional students in India is increasing day by day, therefore there must be proper planning and decision making for their proper development and success. In India more than 90% of people are residing in villages, therefore do not have proper access to all the facilities of education and opportunities but out of all these odds parents are trying their level best to provide them all the required training which can help these students to develop themselves. Professionals are professionally skilled students who are responsible for solving problems. Their main focus is on making things work efficiently and effectively by applying the theories and principles of sciences and arts to research, and develop economic solutions to professional and non-professional problems. The professionals apply their knowledge to solve real problems, often with an eye toward improving cost and efficiency. The purpose of these students is to innovate, design, create and maintain products, system and equipment for the benefit and wellbeing of humans. Their works are the link between the perceived social needs and economic

applications. They are the bridge between science and art.

Professionals are the backbone of nation building and the purpose of these people is to innovate, design, create and maintain the benefit and wellbeing of humans. If a country fails to realize the role of professionals in the nation building then the country will continue to experience collapsed buildings and bridges, substandard products, failed roads, communication failures, environmental hazards, epileptic power supply to mention, poor health ,substandard education system, uncontrolled population, poverty, unemployment, gender inequality, child labour, disturbed legal rules and regulations etc. As a nation we are undergoing reformation and the economy is getting more modernized, consumption patterns have expanded and demand is constantly on the increase. There is therefore a growing consciousness of quality control at every level of production. The professionals have to realize their responsibility and play an effective role in tackling today's complex issues in the nation building. To build a nation is to make it habitable for the citizen by providing social amenities, infrastructural facilities, job creation and security and many more; the professionals therefore have a serious role to play. Thus, they are duty bond to design infrastructure, roadways, railways, products, machineries, medical amenities and facilities, code of conduct, business systems etc.to ensure and strengthen quality and efficiency of the standard of society as a whole.

Professionals should equally know that it is their duty to develop and implement improved ways to extract, process and use the resources that can improve product and services performance and take advantage of advance in technology to harness the quality and standard of living of human beings. They need to analyse the impact of the products and services they develop or systems they design on the environment and the people. They have to find ways of managing the nation's waste, converting or recycling them to useful products. They are really the backbone of a nation's building and development, and their role should not be neglected in a nation's development. The professionals on their part should be proud of what they do and contribute effectively towards the growth of their country and the world at large. Statistics show that the developing countries which have a huge skilled population could be seeing tremendous growth in all the sectors of the countries provided they invest in people's education, health and protect and guarantee their rights. It is believed that today's young minds are tomorrow's leaders, creators, builders, and innovators. For students to be good leaders, inventors and innovators, it is important that they are supported and are provided good health, training, and education to transform the future. There will be a boost in the economy of the country when the Youth is working and earning rather than being dependent on anyone. Professional students are the architect of developing India and scope of these skilled students in India is approximately 80 per cent of the business sector. They need to remove evils from the society such as

gambling, drinking, smoking, litigation, superstition, untouchability, illiteracy, adulteration, corruption and dowry system. They should create in them a spirit of service towards their own country.

While designing a product and services professional must consider effective use of resources with paying attention to the environmental issues and sustainability of resources. They play an important role in sustainable development by overcoming worldwide challenges such as environmental degradation, rapid population growth, and depletion of natural resources. This causes serious issue of balancing between needs of society and preservation of our eco system. Their role is crucial in satisfying needs, health, and welfare of society with minimum or no wastage of resources while preserving environment and sustainability of resources.

In India, many of the institute manufactures millions of professionals every year. But most of them want to do work in a foreign country only for the life style and salary. We made these professionals, but they work in other nations. We have best medical college, IIM's, IIT's etc. in India, which manufacture the world's top class students, but these professionals are not working for us they work in another country. When we take an example of America then there are mostly Indians working on the higher post and developing new technology. Now just think about that if they all are coming back in our country and start doing work for us then think about the speed of growth or development in India. Developing India wants good Professionals to manufacture best product and services at cheaper rates

using the technology. When every youth work in our country, no one will sleep without eating food. All most every company in our country needs good professionals for improving their quality by adding innovation and creativity. We as a responsible citizen should understand the need of our service to our country and try to transform our country to a developed country with our effort and interest. Today's generation are blessed up with greater potential along with the capability of making a nation to progress in each and every aspect.

3. Conclusion:

Professional education is an important tool for industrial growth and sustainable development of any nation. Professional education helps in reduction of unemployment, reduction in country's foreign exchange bill (because goods are produced locally due to better professional skills and trained manpower), reduction in poverty and social inequality in the society. It provides skills for "living, learning and working" which is necessary for responsible and good citizens of a country. The development of a country depends upon the how she use its natural resources. A skill labour force is required to transform country's natural resources into useful product and for that professional education is very much essential. Therefore country can prosper and develop sustainably only if its people become more serious and vigilant in developing the country through professional know-how, skill and competitive recourses.

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CONTRIBUTION OF PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS FOR NATION DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

It is axiomatic to posit that there is a linkage between student and national integration. The role of professional student on national development cannot be over emphasised. The wheel of development of any country lies on the shoulder of how productive and creative they are. Each of us is known by our name, or the language we speak, or the traditions and belief systems we have, and as a group when we are identified or might be related to, we are termed a Nation, which brings us all together. That encourages us to work together to make our country a better place since our lives are intrinsically linked to it.

Keywords: National integration, Professional student, Nation Development, Language.

1. Introduction:

Each of us is known by our name, or the language we speak, or the traditions and belief systems we have, and as a group when we are identified or might be related to, we are termed a Nation, which brings us all together. That encourages us to work together to make our country a better place since our lives are intrinsically linked to it. The welfare of the nation is our welfare. For our own benefit and survival, we must nourish it and keep the flag flying high. Let us consider the big picture and build our future. Whether we are professional accountants, engineers, surgeons, teachers, or any other occupation, we all have an obligation to contribute to society. For the simple reason that this is our country, our home, and we must do everything in our power to make it a great one.

2. Creation of a nation building:

a. Ethics: Having integrity, objectivity, professional competence and ensuring due care is taken to perform the duties as per the standards or guidelines are the basic ethical requirements. But when it comes to choosing between overall good of the society or welfare of the client (and thereby forego the commercial interests), to have enough courage and confidence to do the right thing. I always feel to be 'right ' is different from being 'righteous'.

b. Industrious: Essential to work with diligence and be creative. Bring out solutions which are economical, sustainable and scalable. Look beyond the horizon and think for the next generation. It is essential to encourage and participate in decision or policy.

c. Skill improvement: Two quotes sum up the whole point. (i) Alvin Toffler said, 'the illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and re-learn' and (ii) Abraham Lincoln was quoted as saying "Give me six hours to chop down a tree and I will spend the first four sharpening the axe". Unless the skills are sharpened, there is a downside risk of us being irrelevant. Hence, skills improvement in both short-term and long-term basis is required. Education is an investment in oneself, but the returns are earned by others as well.

d. Competitive: Develop the attitude to take up the challenge and work towards overcoming it. Competitiveness can be developed by having the right mix of attitude, aptitude and skill set. Healthy competition is good since it brings out the best of the people and for the overall good of society. The world has accepted our leadership qualities, as evident from the biggest entities of the world having Indians as their business head or CEO.

e. Culture and Tolerance: A very important aspect of ourselves. We as a

Nation have a great culture to be proud of. Right from a simple greeting 'Namaste' which many of the outsiders realized was a safer and better way to greet than a handshake (in Covid era), or invariably knowing more languages and getting along with different cultures, India is known to have a unique culture and identity, amongst various other practices, we are brought up with the concept of 'Vasudaiva Kutumbakam'. The welfare of the people and society has always remained our bedrock whilst making decisions.

3. Conclusion:

Let us not lose sight of it, and let us be proud of it. Allow for multiple points of view in all of our judgements. Respect, dissent, and disagreement are all important, but they should not become a roadblock to progress. Our nation is in our hands. Let us band together to take it to new heights. The progress of any country depends on the youth there who play an important responsibility to take the nation on the important path of harmonious development. To keep the spirit of national unity alive, they should rise above all differences.

THE PITFALLS AND SOLUTIONS IN INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

“Education is that which liberates” - An ancient proverb. According to Mahatma Gandhi, this liberation not only means spiritual liberation, but it means freedom from all manners of servitude. Mahatma Gandhi emphasized that persistent questioning and curiosity are the first prerequisites for any education system. A strong education system is the cornerstone of any country's growth and prosperity. Over the last decade, India has made great strides in strengthening its primary education system. Since the conditions or surroundings under which one is exposed to education are

1. Introduction:

India today is the second largest higher education network in the world. Universities in India are set up by the Central or State Governments by means of legislation, while colleges are established by the State Governments or private bodies / trusts. All colleges are affiliated to some university.

2. Types of Universities in India:

There are different types of universities such as:

Central or State Universities: While the former are funded directly by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, the latter

not constant, the education process itself cannot be rigid. While discussing about education system in India, instead of focusing on how the current system can be improved with small changes at the bottom, we discuss about the fallbacks of the entire system and a top-down transformation of the education system by taking a hint from this quote of Albert Einstein – “We cannot solve problems by the same kind of thinking we used when we created them”.

Keywords: India Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), Right to Education Act

are set up and funded by the various state governments.

Deemed Universities:

They enjoy the same academic status and privileges as a university. Examples are the Deccan College of Post Graduate and Research Institute, Pune; Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai; Indian Institute of Sciences, Bangalore; etc.

Institutions of National Importance:

These are university-level institutions that are established or designated by Acts of Parliament and funded by the Central Government. These include the Indian

Institutes of Technology, Indian Institutes of Management and the All India Institute of Medical Sciences, etc. Most universities are 'affiliating universities', which prescribe to the affiliated colleges the admission criteria and courses of study, hold examinations and award degrees. University departments impart postgraduate education and conduct and promote research in a variety of disciplines. Undergraduate and, to some extent, postgraduate instruction is imparted by the colleges affiliated to a particular university.

Classification of Colleges

Colleges in India come under four different categories. This categorization is done on the basis of the kind of courses offered by them (Professional / Vocational) / their ownership status (Private / Government) or their relationship with the university (Affiliated / University owned).

University Colleges

These colleges are managed by the university itself and situated mostly in the university campus.

Government Colleges:

The government colleges are few, only about 15-20 percent of the total. They are managed by State governments. As in case of other colleges, the university to which these colleges are affiliated, conducts their examination, lays down the courses of studies and awards the degrees.

Professional Colleges:

The professional colleges are mostly in the disciplines of medicine, engineering and management. There are few for other

disciplines too. They are sponsored and managed either by the government or by private initiative.

Privately Managed Colleges:

About 70% of the colleges are founded by the privately owned trusts or societies. But these institutes are also governed by the rules and regulations of the university they are affiliated to. Though initially started up as a private initiative, the state government also funds these colleges.

3. Courses offered at Higher Education Level:

Indian Universities offer various courses in the following disciplines.

- Engineering and Technology
- Computer Sciences, Information Technology, Biotechnology and Bio-informatics.
- Medical, Dental, Nursing, Pharmacy and Paramedical.
- Agriculture / Veterinary Sciences, Dairy Technology and Fisheries.
- Arts & Fine Arts, Humanities, Social Sciences, Commerce, Science and Management.
- Hotel Management & Catering Technology, Travel and Tourism.
- Fashion Design & Technology.

The academic programs are offered at Vocational Diploma, Undergraduate, Postgraduate and Doctoral levels.

Distance Education:

In India, there are 66 distance education institutions functioning in 60 universities

besides, 11 open universities offering distance education programs. India Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), New Delhi is one of the mega open universities in the world and caters to around 1 million students around the world.

Vocational Education:

Vocational Education at Certificate level are offered by 1500 vocational institutions in the country in the areas of agriculture, business, commerce, health and Para-medical, home science and humanities in addition to engineering trades.

Undergraduate courses, in general, are of three years leading to Bachelor degrees. The universities and higher education institutes award Bachelor's degree in Arts, Science, Commerce, etc. However, undergraduate courses leading to a first degree in professional subjects like Engineering, Medicine, Dentistry and Pharmacy are of a longer duration ranging from four to five and a half years. Most of the engineering courses are for duration of four years, while the medical courses are for duration of about five and a half years.

Postgraduate Courses:

Postgraduate Courses in Arts, Science, Engineering and Medicine are usually for two years ending with the award of a Master's degree. In some specialized fields for instance, for a Bachelor of Education (B. Ed) degree, the possession of a Bachelor's degree in any discipline is required before admission can be obtained. Some universities and higher institutes offer a diploma or a certificate course of shorter duration courses in disciplines like Engineering, Agricultural Sciences and

Computer Technology. However the duration of these courses varies from university to university.

Doctoral Courses:

Doctoral courses like M Phil and PhD are available only at the university colleges. These courses involve research work under a chosen/allotted guide, leading to thesis submission and viva-voce. Successful completion of PhD course designates the title of 'Doctor' to the individual.

4. Expenditure on Education: In terms of expenditure incurred on education, particularly on higher education, during the year 2010-11, the government spent around Rs.15,440 crore which is about 85 per cent of the revised budget estimates for the year. The recent 66th round of NSSO survey reveals that between 1999 and 2009, spending on education in general jumped by 378 per cent in rural areas and 345 per cent in urban areas of the country. The survey further reveals that spending on children's education underlines sharp increase— 63 per cent for rural and 73 per cent for urban families. However, if we measure the expenses on education as a percentage to GDP, India lags behind some developed/developing nations (Table 1). We recognize that the gap in investments in education in India can perhaps be filled by private sector playing a crucial role.

5. Faulty Education Policies:

Earlier, it was the British education policy which served the British Empire; today the education policy favors those who are rich and affluent. The majority of the Indian population is poverty stricken. Government Schools for these have a poor management

and poor quality of education. Much of the quality education is provided by private schools affiliated to CBSE and CISCE whose curriculum is advanced and in conformity with the worldwide education system. Not all are able to afford these schools and are deprived of quality education. Education policies are also misused by Politicians who try to mould these to achieve their political motives. A glaring example is that of the BJP's influence to mould the syllabus of the schools. It was in 2000/01, that NCERT (National Council of Educational Research and Training) issued a National Curriculum Framework for school education. Under this framework all foreign elements including those of the Britishers and moguls were removed. Textbooks were revised and these presented a distorted history. The revision presented an outlook of India as a Hindu nation painted with Religious and regional tones. There were protest against this Hindu-centric education and by 2004; the old books replaced the faulty books.

6. Political and Bureaucratic Involvement:

Majority of the Politician and Bureaucrats have age which makes them senior citizens. Some of them are not educated, some are partially or have received ineffective education, and some have reached this far because of their affluence and not ability. Thus, we have illiterate politicians handling education department, orthodox bureaucrats who are resistant to new ideas and experimentation. Education is Business for the Politicians and Manipulation Tool for bureaucrats. Seats are reserved for the likes of these, leaving deserving ones biting the

dust. Selfish motives make them blind to achieve the more important nation's motive. Power and control are great weapons and if those controlling it are selfish and corrupt, there is slim chance that they will be dethroned in short span of time.

7. Conclusion:

We can see that there is lot of scope for the present education system to improve. In depth analysis can reveal better ways and methods for improvement. With better and informed action from government and society the current system of education can surely be made more excellent and inclusive with much wider expanse. First of all, the content of our syllabus, both in school level as well as college level should get updated with the changing world so that we people don't stay back dated. Secondly, innovation (the thing we lack) should always be encouraged and given a place in the first row so that students can fully express themselves to their potential. Thirdly, we should be emphasized more on English language from the early stage of study in an efficient manner so students don't face any kinds of communication problems (the most youth face today) as there will be globalization in near future. In case of technical courses, we should be given access to more on practical knowledge rather than theoretical. India's private-schooled, English-speaking urban elite may attract global attention, but they are in the minority. Besides, taking a leaf from the western hemisphere, India should try to become 'knowledge economy' to promote inclusive growth. I, therefore, would like underline three major areas to be focused to ensure that our education system is sustainable and meets global standards:

- Quality of Education – In terms of infrastructure, teachers, accreditation, etc.
- Affordability of Education – Ensuring poor and deserving students are not denied education.
- Ethics in Education – Avoiding over-commercialization of education system.

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THE ROLE OF STUDENTS IN THE SOCIETY

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Abstract:

Years spent as a student constitute the most impressionable of times wherein an individual garners essential knowledge, much-needed skill and life experiences while forming valuable relationships. Undoubtedly thus, students are the most important components of society. This position elevates their social responsibility to an altogether higher degree wherein their duty as responsible students in their community shapes social structure, functioning and allied determinants. It is indeed undeniable that one cannot live in complete isolation from society and so applies to a student as well. One is in a constant state of give and take from society. Thereby the intermediary links constructed between a student and the social structure thus influence the importance of students in society making them significant contributors.

Keywords: Society, literacy, Community

1. Contribution to Literacy:

The realm of literacy in the social structure has always been a grave cause of concern wherein a large stratum of society remains devoid of the right to literacy. This deprivation is resultant of various factors such as that of poverty, unemployment, lack of awareness, gender and caste discrimination etc. Thus, the role of students in modern society that takes into account literacy as the determinant of a secure future is to ensure that they in different ways contribute to teaching the illiterate, motivating one and all to take the leap towards education and strengthening the foundations of the nation. Literacy campaigns, libraries, book exchanges, community literacy programmes and so on

are not a distant dream if the student community vows to furnish their social responsibility.

2. Fight Against Antisocial Activities:

Crucial concerns of modern society stem from a rise in antisocial activities and their hazardous consequences. Theft, corruption, murder, black marketing, exploitation of women, weaker sections, rape and harassment compromise safe living standards as well as tarnish the social image. In such a scenario, the ambition of students must be to work towards the total eradication of these social disabilities. With the rise of social media, the right to speak up in democracy and the consolidation of student power, adequate solutions can be implemented to put an end to these burning

social issues and thereby promote an equal, harmonious and lawful society. The aim of social welfare is yet another goal which is realized through blood donation camps, relief funds, tending to the sick, needy and destitute, offering vulnerable animals a home and developing a sense of helpfulness, kindness and moral responsibility towards the society. Students in modern society must therefore be a catalyst for change and actualization of social welfare.

3. Say No to Drugs and Alcohol:

Drug and alcohol addiction has long since blinded youth, deviated individuals from a healthy, progressive life and most of all led to a number of personal and social problems. Addictions paralyze an individual, metaphorically if not physically and so hinder personal growth, kill ambition and engulf one in a sense of nothingness and denial. Used as an escape mechanism, drugs and alcohol disrupt family life, and happiness, lead to poverty and stunt the contribution of individuals to the nation. The drive of students thus must be to educate, sensitize and promote addiction-free living through various mediums such as that campaigns, street plays, social media, talks, volunteering at NGOs and de-addiction centres and so on.

4. Pioneers of Technological Advancements:

Scientific advancement, innovation and novelty are the factors that make a nation stand out from the rest in the modern world. With young minds bubbling with a scientific temperament, drive to discover, and strive for innovation and progress, the contribution of students to society is thus exercised.

Young scientists in space organizations, students who have made innovations beyond their age, child prodigies, young interns with a zeal to learn and grow, and students who have opened up classes to educate their underprivileged contemporaries; there is active and noteworthy participation from the student community.

5. Pride of The Nation:

Young achievers making their mark in the arena of sports and athletics thereby add to their role as student contributors as promoters of physical fitness, national pride and integral value systems. Sports builds confidence, the ability to make decisions, not crack under pressure, to be a great leader and most of all, to build meaningful relationships. Young individuals with an enthusiasm for sports are thus ambassadors of fitness and overall wellbeing. Quite many have made the nation proud on various state, national and international platforms. Mehuli Ghosh, a 17-year-old shooter has made the nation proud with her debut in the Commonwealth Games at Gold Coast and also won eight gold medals on various platforms thereafter.

6. Sustainable Development:

With the rise of climate change, pollution and other ecological imbalances, calamities and disasters have become a common factor in present times. As catalysts of change, students in our society incline towards an active contribution to disaster prevention and management. In a capitalistic society, development is usually exploitative in a way that it is absolutely capital oriented and does not in any way take into account other side effects. Thus, as responsible students who

have imbibed something from their extensive and industrious syllabus, one must be able to move towards a sustainable development that not only takes into account modern needs but also saves enough for future generations.

7. Strong Value System:

As the pioneers of change, students must work to annihilate caste, the evils of untouchability and promote gender equality. The caste and gender conflict has been at the heart of the Indian psyche since times immemorial. Thereby, atrocities based on caste and gender hierarchy have impacted and destroyed the lives of men and women depriving them of opportunities, privileges, freedoms and the right to a decent standard of living. As responsible citizens, students as a part of the community must navigate alternate ways of living, rising above gender, caste, religion and everything that holds us back.

8. Ecological Responsibility:

Pollution has changed the world in ways that to a large extent cannot be reversed. Inconsistent rainfall patterns and soil erosion owing to deforestation, melting ice caps and rising sea levels due to ozone rupture, alarming natural phenomena and unpredictable weather patterns resultant from pollution; the balance of nature is under threat. Numerous plant and animal species are on the verge of extinction while the survival of man is largely a threat. Thus, students are habituated to these issues, equipped to tackle them in their little ways, indulge in afforestation, water and soil conservation, cut down on pollution and so

on. Their curriculum consists therefore of extensive environmental studies so that they may be better able to exercise their role as students.

9. Service to The Nation:

It is the duty of each and every citizen of the nation to serve the country at any time required. The members of the defence forces of the Army, Navy and Airforce strive hard for the protection of each and every citizen of the nation, sacrificing their own lives. There is no nobler profession than that of the defence forces and doctors. The youth first as student role models and later as doctors, engineers, scientists and government servants with their political sensibilities, can contribute to the nation.

10. The Voice of Society:

The power of youth is such that their voice will be heard in society and thereby they can speak up for the marginalized, work for social good, place demands and have them sanctioned. The duty of students must be to act as role models for others in the society and the generations to come and thereby make society a better place to live in.

11. Conclusion:

In a constant engagement of give and take, students need to meet up to certain expectations of society. In their life span, students do take a lot from parents, teachers and society at large. Thus, it becomes their moral responsibility to exercise their role as students in society and turn into productive members, building a secure future for themselves and society.

EVOLUTION OF CAREER SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Career services in higher education has evolved since its inception and adapted to various models following economic conditions, trends and demands of the labor market, and needs of the university and society. In the early 1900s, there were vocations bureaus, created to help new immigrants find work. In the 1920s and 1930s, vocational guidance for teachers emerged out of the need for more teachers. In the 1940s and through the 1960s, the need to match GI Bill veterans to jobs allowed for new job placement centers to emerge on college campuses. The 1970s and 1980s brought career planning and counseling centers, which focused on helping students and graduates explore careers and plan their own job search. The information technology and social media revolution of the 1990s and 2000s later transformed career centers into dynamic networking hubs that engaged hiring organizations in campus recruiting and facilitated networking between students and recruiters.

Keywords: Evolution, Higher education

1. Introduction:

Career services in higher education has evolved since its inception and adapted to various models following economic conditions, trends and demands of the labor market, and needs of the university and society.

2. Vocational Guidance and Teachers Guidance:

Career guidance in higher education can be traced back to the emergence of vocational guidance in the early 1900s and the creation of Frank Parson's first career center, the Vocations Bureau, in the Civic Service House in Boston, MA, a public service entity that helped new immigrants transition to life in America (Vinson, Reardon, & Bertoch, 2011). In the 1920s

and 1930s, industrialization and a post-World War I baby boom created an influx of students, which increased the need for educational and vocational guidance for graduating teachers (Vinson et al., 2011), slowly moving faculty away from their mentoring roles. Vocational guidance still remained absent in more than half of colleges and universities in the United States (Pope, 2000).

Job Placement. The landscape of higher education and career guidance changed once again post-World War II in the 1940s and 1950s. A booming economy and greater employer demand for candidates juxtaposed with the need to place graduating war veterans who returned to college on the GI Bill accelerated the transformation of vocational guidance into the placement

paradigm and the expansion of placement centers in higher education (Casella, 1990). Using Parson's trait-and-factor theory as a theoretical foundation, placement centers were responsible for matching graduates' abilities and interests with job criteria (Kretovicks, Honaker, & Kraning, 1999).

Career Counseling. In the 1970s and 1980s, as higher education shifted into a development model, which placed the responsibility of learning and educational outcomes on the student, a slowing economy and increased competition for candidates changed the landscape for career services once again (Kretovicks et al., 1999). This paradigm shift forced students to take ownership of their own career development and job search, and recruiters to manage their own "matching process." This allowed career centers to step back into the guidance space with more emphasis on counseling, career planning, and job search preparation (Casella, 1990). The self-actualization movement of the 1970s and 1980s continued to strengthen the counseling model in career services, which heightened the clinician identity among staff and shifted the director's profile from a placement manager to a counseling supervisor.

Professional Networking. In the 1990s and 2000s, the dot-com boom increased the competition for candidates on college campuses, which helped reengage career centers in employer relations and helped transform them into comprehensive career services offices that facilitated the relationship between students and employers through various networking career events and recruiting activities (Dey &

Real, 2010). New information technologies accelerated this process through the continuous development of recruiting software, and social media began to redefine how students make meaning of their experience and connect with employers and professional communities.

Emerging Trends:

Similar to the last four paradigm shifts of college career services in the 20th century, the current transformation in career services requires the acquisition of additional resources, elevating the leadership of career centers to higher levels of influence, designing new and creative organizational structures, and establishing stronger coordinated campus partnerships.

Elevation of Career Services: Senior leaders in higher education are beginning to recognize the direct link career services has to recruitment, retention, and revenue for an institution (Ceperley, 2013; Education Advisory Board, 2012). As a result, many are elevating career services, giving their leadership more institutional influence and the ability to convene internal and external stakeholders in order to help students leverage the power of the university network. Elevation includes changes to titles, reporting lines, and resources.

While leaders, regardless of titles, need to exercise savvy leadership to gain buy-in and demonstrate value, positional power adds a layer of systemic and organizational support that is also necessary to elevate career services in higher education over time. Titles for many leaders in career services are beginning to take the form of assistant/associate vice

presidents/ provosts, deans, and associate deans. Recent examples of elevated college career services include University of Chicago, Stanford, University of South Florida, University of Virginia, Wake Forest, and William and Mary. This change has allowed institutions to more accurately represent the scope of responsibility and accountability placed on career services. Uniquely positioned as one of few units within a university that must actively engage with all academic deans, senior leadership, boards of trustees, advancement, the external community, and other campus partners, the upgraded title further illustrates the institution's support and value for career services.

Outcomes and Accountability: The conversation about return on investment and value of higher education has never been more prominent (Carlson, 2013; The Economist, 2014). It is critical for all career centers to develop clear strategic plans that align with institutional priorities (Contomanolis & Steinfeld, 2014), to determine key resulting outcomes, and to define key performance indicators. The ability to effectively collect data and craft a compelling story will become a standard operating practice. The measures of success for career services are shifting to first-destination data, reputation, and engagement of key stakeholders.

With the new NACE First-Destination Survey Standards and Protocols (NACE, 2014), guidelines have been provided to help institutions collect data in a more standardized manner. While some leaders of career services are still hesitant to engage in conversations about placement

or career outcomes, the most successful career centers will be those that embrace the occasion to play a lead role in the collection and dissemination of information. Career services leaders have the unique ability to use first-destination data as a catalyst for university-wide discussion on how all stakeholders can play defined and active roles in supporting the career readiness of students (Contomanolis & Steinfeld, 2014).

First-destination and career outcomes data only tell part of the story, and career services must continue to illustrate additional value added by showcasing metrics on reputation, referral, and engagement of key stakeholders. As noted previously, the ability for career services to connect and create communities will lead to greater student success, and therefore, measuring the reputation of the career center and staff becomes a critical assessment of success. Stanford University now measures the reputation of its career center and staff using a net promoter score, a popular metric in the retail and business. Career services must be willing to ask stakeholders for feedback on how they are perceived and their willingness to refer. As networks begin to grow, career services will also need to showcase the breadth and depth of stakeholder engagement.

Branding. Establishing presence, creating a culture of career readiness, and showcasing institutional value require a high level of brand recognition—both for employers and career services. For employers, the need to build a cohesive and compelling brand on campus is core

to an effective recruitment strategy (NACE, 2013). The best marketing tool continues to be word of mouth, and an employer's image among students can heavily impact recruiting efforts on any given campus. Career services professionals have the opportunity to play a vital role in helping employers differentiate from competitors and speak to the values that are most prominent for the institution.

New Breed of College Career Services Staff:

A paradigm shift in college career services requires career staff to not only upgrade their skills and knowledge, but also change their attitudes and philosophy about the new needs of their stakeholders and how to help students transition from college to career. The new emphasis on connections and communities requires an identity shift from counselor to group facilitator and expert consultant. Workshops are no longer effective. Instead, career staff must think of less formal and more interactive meet-ups that take place in various student "hot spots" around campus. Rather than a strategy of outreach and promotions, they must create a brand for themselves and their departments. Protecting the career center's turf is also a strategy of the past. Instead, the focus should be on leveraging the entire campus ecosystem through partnerships and collaboration.

The Future: Connected Communities:

The emerging trends discussed in this chapter further highlight the ever-evolving environment and the need for career services to embrace and drive change. Through

relationship building and creating strong career communities within and beyond campus, career services can provide customized approaches and stronger outcomes for institutions. With growing accountability in higher education and the opportunity to activate a wide network of stakeholders, this current paradigm positions career services to play a critical role in the recruitment, retention, and postgraduate success of students.

As career centers gain more influence in their campus communities and become better resources and more connected to all their stakeholders, they will be better equipped to engage students early and often within their communities, offer them specialized career development support, and connect them to internship and employment opportunities as well as mentoring and experiential learning. Career and professional development will continue to rise as a critical part of the fabric of the student experience rather than a resource that they seek when they approach graduation.

Conclusions:

It is important to view the evolution of career services in higher education as continuous building blocks that maintain the integrity of past models and build upon them as new ones emerge rather than a process of letting go. For example, the shift from the counseling and planning paradigm to networking does not mean that counseling is dead in career services. On the contrary, counseling may be a critical intervention in the new networking model, although it is no longer the

emphasis of the model. Likewise, the transition from placement to counseling does not completely dismiss the candidate–employer matching procedure, which remains a critical operational element, but no longer the central mission of a career center.

Every paradigm shift presents a set of great challenges for career centers, but the opportunities to redesign their mission and attain higher relevance and more resources in their institutions are greater. Visionary leadership helps present career centers and their staff as the solution to the pressures and challenges that colleges and universities experience as a result of changes in the economy or other environmental factors. Outcomes that align with the institution’s strategic priorities help stakeholders, such as faculty and alumni, view career centers beyond the transactional procedures for which they are responsible.

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RESPONSIBILITIES OF PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS IN CAREER BUILDING

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Abstract:

Professional students play a vital role in nation building by leveraging their knowledge, skills, and expertise to drive innovation, economic growth, social development, and effective governance. Their contributions across different sectors and their ability to address complex challenges make them invaluable assets for the progress and prosperity of a nation. By embodying these qualities and behaviors, students can develop a strong foundation of professionalism, which will contribute to their academic success, prepare them for the workplace, and enhance their overall career prospects.

Keywords: Professional students, carrier building

1. Introduction:

Professional students are individuals who are pursuing higher education in specialized fields that require specific knowledge and skills. These fields typically include disciplines such as medicine, law, engineering, business, technology, and other professional areas. Professional students undergo rigorous academic training and practical experiences to become experts in their chosen fields. Professional students can be found in various educational institutions such as universities, colleges, and professional schools. They often pursue advanced degrees such as Master's or Doctoral degrees or professional certifications that qualify them for specific roles and professions. The role of professional students extends beyond acquiring knowledge and skills in their

respective fields. They play a crucial role in shaping the future of their professions and making significant contributions to society.

2. Role of Students in Career Building:

Students play a vital role in building their careers and setting the foundation for their professional growth. Here are some key aspects highlighting the role of students in career building:

1. **Self-Exploration:** Students have the opportunity to explore their interests, strengths, and passions during their academic journey. They can engage in various activities, courses, internships, and extracurricular pursuits to gain a better understanding of their career preferences. By exploring different fields, students can make informed decisions about their career paths.

2. Goal Setting: Students play a crucial role in setting their career goals. They need to define their short-term and long-term objectives, establish milestones, and create a roadmap for achieving their desired career outcomes. Setting clear goals helps students stay focused, motivated, and accountable for their career development.

3. Skill Development: Students can actively work on developing the necessary skills for their chosen careers. Along with the technical skills specific to their field, students should also focus on acquiring transferable skills such as communication, problem-solving, teamwork, leadership, and adaptability. Enhancing these skills enhances their employability and opens up more opportunities.

4. Networking: Building and nurturing professional networks is crucial for career development. Students can actively engage in networking activities by attending career fairs, industry events, joining professional associations, and connecting with professionals in their desired fields. Networking helps students gain insights, access job opportunities, and build relationships that can support their career growth.

5. Building a Professional Brand: Students can start building their professional brand even before entering the workforce. They can develop an online presence through platforms like LinkedIn, create a professional portfolio, and showcase their achievements and projects. Building a strong professional brand helps students stand out to potential employers and demonstrates their expertise and capabilities.

3. Role of professional students in Nation building:

Professional students play a crucial role in nation building by contributing their knowledge, skills, and expertise to various sectors and industries. These students are typically pursuing higher education in fields such as engineering, medicine, law, business, technology, and other specialized areas. Here are some ways in which professional students contribute to nation building:

1. Innovation and Research: Professional students often engage in research and innovation activities that lead to the development of new technologies, processes, and solutions. Their work can have a direct impact on improving the quality of life, driving economic growth, and addressing societal challenges.

2. Skilled Workforce: Professional students receive specialized education and training in their respective fields. As they graduate and enter the workforce, they bring their expertise and skills to industries, making them more productive and competitive. This contributes to the growth of various sectors and boosts the overall economy.

3. Entrepreneurship and Job Creation: Professional students often have a strong entrepreneurial spirit. They can start their own businesses and ventures, creating job opportunities for others. By launching innovative startups and enterprises, they contribute to economic development, generate employment, and promote a culture of entrepreneurship.

4. Professional Services: Many professional students become professionals

in their fields, such as doctors, engineers, lawyers, architects, and consultants. By providing their services, they contribute to the development of infrastructure, healthcare, legal systems, and other essential sectors, ultimately improving the overall functioning of the nation.

5. Policy and Governance: Professional students often have a deep understanding of their respective fields, which makes them valuable contributors to policy-making and governance processes. They can offer insights, expertise, and research-based recommendations that shape policies, regulations, and frameworks for various sectors, leading to effective governance and sustainable development.

6. Social Impact and Community Engagement: Professional students can actively engage with communities and contribute to social welfare. They can participate in volunteer activities, offer pro bono services, and work on initiatives addressing social issues. Their knowledge and skills can be utilized to improve education, healthcare, environmental sustainability, and other aspects of society.

7. Global Collaboration and Diplomacy: In an interconnected world, professional students often engage in international collaborations, research partnerships, and exchange programs. These interactions foster global understanding, cultural exchange, and cooperation, leading to advancements in various fields and contributing to diplomacy and international relations.

Students and professionalism

Professionalism is a set of attitudes, behaviors, and qualities that students should cultivate to succeed in their academic and professional pursuits. Here are some key aspects of professionalism that students should focus on:

1. Responsibility and Accountability: Professional students take responsibility for their actions, assignments, and commitments. They meet deadlines, complete tasks with diligence, and take ownership of their work. They are accountable for their performance and strive for excellence in all aspects of their academic and professional lives.

2. Ethical Conduct: Professional students uphold high ethical standards in their interactions with peers, faculty, staff, and professionals in their field. They demonstrate integrity, honesty, and respect for others. They adhere to academic integrity policies, maintain confidentiality when necessary, and conduct themselves in an ethical and professional manner.

3. Communication Skills: Effective communication is essential for professional students. They should be able to articulate their thoughts and ideas clearly and professionally, both in written and verbal forms. They actively listen to others, ask questions, and engage in respectful and constructive dialogue. Good communication skills help professional students collaborate effectively and build strong professional relationships.

4. Time Management: Professional students prioritize their time and manage their schedules efficiently. They balance their academic responsibilities with other

commitments, such as part-time jobs, internships, and extracurricular activities. They understand the importance of meeting deadlines and allocate time appropriately to complete tasks and assignments.

5. **Adaptability and Flexibility:** Professional students demonstrate adaptability and flexibility in response to changes and challenges. They embrace new technologies, methodologies, and approaches to learning. They are open to feedback and constructive criticism and use it to improve their skills and performance.

6. **Professional Appearance:** Professional students understand the importance of presenting themselves in a professional manner. They dress appropriately for academic and professional settings, following any specific dress codes or guidelines. They maintain personal hygiene and grooming standards that align with professional expectations.

7. **Teamwork and Collaboration:** Professional students work effectively in teams, respecting diverse perspectives and contributing their expertise. They actively participate in group projects, share responsibilities, and communicate constructively to achieve common goals.

They demonstrate professionalism by being reliable, supportive, and fostering a positive team environment.

8. **Lifelong Learning:** Professional students recognize the value of continuous learning and professional development. They actively seek opportunities to expand their knowledge and skills through internships, workshops, conferences, and professional associations. They stay updated with industry trends, emerging technologies, and best practices in their field

4. Conclusion:

Overall, professional students play a vital role in nation building by leveraging their knowledge, skills, and expertise to drive innovation, economic growth, social development, and effective governance. Their contributions across different sectors and their ability to address complex challenges make them invaluable assets for the progress and prosperity of a nation. By embodying these qualities and behaviors, students can develop a strong foundation of professionalism, which will contribute to their academic success, prepare them for the workplace, and enhance their overall career prospects.

STUDENT'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR BUILDING STRONG NATION

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Abstract

Students, the future of a nation, play a very vital role in nation building. Every individual countryman can play its role in nation building by doing his duties in right manner. We already knew that the future of country or of a nation fully depends upon its citizens, so there is a great need of healthy minds. This is possible only when the discipline is inculcated by making the students aware of their duties and responsibilities. For making young generation an integral part of nation building, the seeds of discipline must be sown in their minds through moral values. Whatever knowledge is being acquired by the student's that should be utilized for the betterment of self, society and the nation.

Keywords: Students, Nation, Citizens, Nation building, Duties and responsibilities.

1. Introduction:

We know that the future of country or of a nation fully depends upon its citizens so there is a great need of healthy minds. This is possible only when the discipline is inculcated by making the students aware of their duties and responsibilities. For making young generation an integral part of nation building, the seeds of discipline must be sown in their minds through moral values. Whatever knowledge is being acquired by the student's that should be utilized for the betterment of self, society and the nation. Student's prime duty is towards their teachers and parents. The education system must stress on the all round development of the students.

2. Responsibility of students:

In Nationhood, people play a very important role. Naturally, Students are an important part of it. Students are the spring of life. They are young, energetic and vibrant, can easily achieve a lot and can do many things for the society. They carry the power to

transform the nation into a better place. They also have the ability to lead their fellow citizens in the right direction. A good seed always grow to a good tree, and only a good tree can give a good fruit. A student will eventually become a good citizen; a good citizens will makes a better society. The vision and progress of our country lies in the hands of our students.

People are grown trees whereas students are seeds. A good seed gives a good tree, good tree gives good fruit. A student becomes a good citizen; a good citizen makes a better society.

The formula for great nation is "Good student > virtuous society > great nation". A good student forms a virtuous society means which is graft-less, politically balanced, economically standard and stands on moral Grounds. The nation with integrity stands forever. The students are prospective heirs of nation. So they should be well equipped with sound moral, political and economical views. They are the pillars on which

beautiful edifices will be built. Students must have these qualities – a) Desire to win
b) Courage to do things
c) Wisdom to understand and unravel the problems.

To play their role properly we should teach the youth of our country to make themselves disciplined. They should not be led away by the anti- national forces. They should not go astray in their schools and colleges. In all, the teachers and professor may fill the students' hearts with idealism. The young man should learn lessons of hard work, high morality, books as may create such ideals.

Students are vital organs of nation. They are future citizens, who can become “Nation’s most needed” categories i.e. producers, protectors, philosophers etc. Producers produce the needed items which may be related to food, electronic, engineering arenas etc. Protectors protect the nation. Philosophers guide the nation. Student must invigilate his environment. He must be active in every field. He should participate in politics also. According to Plato, “Education should be given up to 25 years at the elementary level and up to 35 years at the higher level. This is to cure mental malady by mental medicine.” If a student does not participate in every field, it will be turned into a river which has no flow. It will be house for algae, frogs and formidable insects.

The students must understand that they are students and should pay full attention to their studies. They should devote a greater part of their time to the pursuit of knowledge and wisdom. They should play for them to learn and to prepare themselves for future responsibilities in life. Without good education they will not be able to shoulder their future burdens.

Students should cultivate in them good manners and purity of life. They should not follow only intellectual knowledge, but also from their moral character.

Obedience to parents, respect for teachers, and sympathy for the poor, love for all and malice towards none should be their chief moral ideals. They should be refined in their taste, sweet in their speech and polite in their behavior.

Conclusion:

In a nutshell, students' role is to get ready for adult responsibilities. He is tasked with ridding society of vices as child marriage, gambling, drinking, smoking, lawsuits, superstition, untouchability, illiteracy, adultery, corruption, and the dowry system. They ought to cultivate a sense of altruism in them. Future leaders and rulers of our nation are students. They act as the nation's reserve force. They serve as the foundation of the nation. Our nation's youth depends on our pupils.

TECHNICAL INNOVATION USED IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

As per Dr. S. R. Ranganathan, the library is a mounting establishment. The libraries have changed due to the innovative technology's revolution. Nowadays, Libraries are providing needed materials usually to researchers and user faster and easier. There are lots of new technologies which are using in overseas. In India, libraries are using new technologies but it is less than other countries. Drowns, Robots, Artificial Intelligence etc are not used in India.

Keywords: libraries, cloud printing, nimble technology

1. Introduction:

Even in today's digital age, this law holds true. The traditional library is being converted into a digital library and the new name library is being used in the library today and the name of the library has also been changed and it is called Library and Resource Centre instead of library. In the library subsequently, numerous administrations have started using computers in late 1960s. By early 1970s several indexing and conceptualizing journals were available for library submissions, Index Medicus, Chemical abstracts, Biological Summaries etc. Far from being a simple source of books and media, today's libraries serve as irreplaceable properties for everything from data analytics to 3-D printing and opening lessons in coding. Today modern library to take in the changing faces of its patrons and respond consequently. Every demographic is

dissimilar, but there are countless ways that the modern library can answer to recent trends and offer data and resources that are both advanced and pertinent to its users. Digital librarian and self-determining consultant, helps us look at how libraries are using technology to improve facilities for customers today. Advanced libraries are using digital tools like Digital maker labs offer customers the chance to learn and use some of the most cutting-edge technology.

2. Technical innovation used in libraries:

There are new innovation techniques used in libraries.

(i) Digital Maker Labs:

Digital maker labs offer customers the chance to learn and use some of the most cutting edge technology around. From 3D printers, Computer controlled CNC routers, to hot presses for Tshirts and Laser cutter-engravers, Maker Labs are popping up in

libraries all over the UK. While it's fair to say you won't see one in every library, chances are your nearest Maker lab won't be too far away.

(ii) RFID Technology

Modernization has become very important in the current situation in the library, in which libraries should be available 24 hours. RFID saves library staff time and effort, as libraries have extended their hours of availability, new form RFID of self-service solutions have emerged in the form of machines or software for different processes. RFID saves time and effort of library staff. Various needs and library work becomes easier in the library by RFID System.

(iii) Cloud Printing

The digital era has been directly affecting home printing. Cloud printing supports mobile working and travelling and means that people can work wherever there is a library rather than needing a traditional office space. It can also attract different kinds of people who might not previously have used a library. Cloud printing has become commonplace in libraries because it gives users the ability to utilize their smart phones, tablets, and laptops to print. Through cloud printing a user can print out even from a remote location

(iv) Robots

There is a number of libraries who have already successfully implemented some kind of automated technology. For example Connecticut's Westport Library, which recently acquired two robots, Vincent and Nancy, that will be used to help teach coding and computer programming skills.

Yes, it is a whole new level of social interaction. Robots are useful in attracting users to the library as well as entertaining them. Library work is also made easier by these robots.

(v) Nimble Technology: Nimble is a Concept of an advanced library augmented reality tool. Designed by a London based interactive designer and Google engineer Suresh Kumar, Nimble dose not only offer digital enhancement of a print book, but also incorporates the idea featured earlier in the post- the turn by-turn library guide, all these features can be accessed using the smart library card, all-in-one solution to let patrons use the digital books to work with whichever content want.

(vi) Library Software:

There lot of library software are available for college libraries like SOUL, SLIM, Libsis, KOHA, LIBRARIAN and many others which helps libraries to Computerize the library.

(vii) Digital, Virtual Library:

A digital library, digital repository, or digital collection, is an online database of digital objects that can include text, still images, audio, video, digital documents, or other digital media formats. The advantages of digital libraries as a means of easily and rapidly accessing books, archives and images of various types are now widely recognized by commercial interests and public bodies alike. Traditional libraries are limited by storage space; digital libraries have the potential to store much more information, simply because digital information requires very little physical space to contain it. As such, the cost of

maintaining a digital library can be much lower than that of a traditional library. A physical library must spend large sums of money paying for staff, book maintenance, rent, and additional books. Digital libraries may reduce or, in some instances, do away with these fees. Both types of library require cataloging input to allow users to locate and retrieve material. Digital libraries may be more willing to adopt innovations in technology providing users with improvements in electronic and audio book technology as well as presenting new forms of communication such as wikis and blogs; conventional libraries may consider that providing online access to their OP AC catalogue is sufficient. An important advantage to digital conversion is increased accessibility to users. They also increase availability to individuals who may not be traditional patrons of a library, due to geographic location or organizational affiliation.

(viii) Virtual Library Tour:

A virtual library tour is a simulation of an existing location, usually composed of a sequence of videos or still images. It may also use other multimedia elements such as sound effects, music, narration, and text. It is distinguished from the use of live television to affect tele-tourism. The virtual tours make the new type of library information products borrowed from the tourist and museum practice. Its essential components, tour types, technologies to be used. Qualitative features which allow expecting their rapid growth and implementation in many spheres, in particular, in libraries, are revealed. Library virtual tours are specified and characterized

based on the study of different types of libraries. For this purpose, the www-sites of 236 libraries were reviewed. Significant divergence in interpreting the term of “virtual tour” in the museum and library spheres is revealed. Virtual tours delivered via the Web have become a common tool for both instruction and outreach. Virtual tours can enhance a library's Web presence as well as provide much needed information to remote or prospective users.

(ix) Big Data

Along with all the technological advancements, people's most basic activities are generating more data than ever. The storage and analysis of large datasets can be a real advantage for librarians as they have the relevant skills and knowledge to make the best use of these massive sources of information. Big data can improve the library's activity overall, by simply having access to more insights into the user's mind.

(x) Digital Storytelling App

Now libraries are working with writers and coders to create new interactive stories where the reader can become immersed and attempt to control the narrative flow. Libraries have always had a love affair with the written word, whether on paper, microfilm, CDROM or web page. Meaning of storytelling is To tell stories is fundamentally human. Storytelling emerged in popular consciousness around the turn of the 21st century. Digital storytelling is the latest iteration of a narrative tradition. It involves creating and sharing stories using digital tools, incorporating multimedia elements such as image, sound, and words in

a narrative that is then disseminated via a web platform.

(xii) Mobile Apps

Mobile apps are a real trend right now, as people have access to their mobile devices constantly. A mobile app can extend the library's services outside their physical borders and facilitate the interaction with patrons. An app that offers functionalities such as a library catalogue, interactive library guides, a library virtual tour, an interactive calendar with all the library's events, the possibility to loan and read electronic books and articles, the possibility to reserve the library's resources or to pay for some services represent a real benefit for the patrons, facilitating their activities at the library.

(xiii) Baggage Carousel

A baggage carousel is a device, generally at an airport, that delivers checked luggage to the passengers at the baggage reclaims area at their final destination. Not all airports use these devices. Airports without carousels generally deliver baggage by placing it on the floor or sliding it through an opening in a wall. Bags are placed on some type of conveyor belt in a secure area not accessible by passengers. In a single-level system, the belt will deliver bags into the terminal from an opening in the wall. The belt generally runs along the wall for a short distance and then turns into the terminal forming a long oval that allows many passengers to access the belt. The belt continues back to the loading area through a second opening in the wall. In a multilevel system, the bags are generally loaded from above or below the carousel and then delivered onto a moving

oval-shaped carousel. It is common for this type of system to have two delivery belts, increasing the speed with which bags can be delivered to the passenger level. This baggage Carousel system also use in libraries. In the Library of S.G.B. Amravati University a baggage carousel device placed and in library they use books in place of bags. They deliver books by placing it on the floor or siding it through an opening in a wall.

3. Conclusion:

The libraries have changed due to the innovative technology's revolution. Nowadays, Libraries are providing needed materials usually to researchers and user faster and easier. There are lot of new technologies which are using in overseas. In India libraries are using new technologies but it is less than other countries. Drowns, Robots, Artificial Intelligence etc are not used in India.

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ROLE OF CIVIL ENGINEERS IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract:

The world is changing faster than ever before and engineers are behind much of the development. Engineers are viewed as the backbone of modern society for almost everything that we use to facilitate our activities is an engineering product. It is difficult to imagine our lives today without computers, phones, cars, trains, aircrafts, motors, or even a sickle or a nail. Naturally, the engineering profession generates a healthy source of income for its practitioners. This puts emphasis on students' preference for engineering courses that make them look up to the world for gainful employment or (a career in) entrepreneurship Engineering covers a wide range of disciplines; a variety of specialties from rockets to wall pins and even medical equipment and submarines. Every engineering degree is challenging, and there are so many different types of engineering degrees that one can certainly find a field that leads to career satisfaction. Whether it's civil, electrical, chemical, mechanical, petroleum, aeronautical, IT, bio tech or medical engineering, the programmes have a place for any aspiring candidate who has an aptitude for tinkering, creating, designing, building and contextual understanding.

Keywords: Civil Engineers, Nation building

1. Introduction:

Studying engineering can lead to excellent career prospects and high salaries across a wide range of industries and the possibility of working on world-changing technological developments. For students with an aptitude for mathematics and science, as well as the ability to solve problems, obtaining a degree in an engineering programme may not only provide them respect and high remuneration but also a career that has long-term potential for growth and opportunities. So engineers tend to do better no matter what sector they choose, and they also tend to make good

managers. Engineers shape the world we live in, from civil infrastructure, manufacturing, healthcare delivery, information management, computer communications, and so on. An education in engineering allows students exposure to various technical subjects and (helps them) develop skills that make them ready for the industries that are rapidly changing the technological environment.

A basic degree in engineering can offer diverse options for master's degree that have stronger connections to the industry and to the social, economic, and management

sciences. One can either opt for a conventional degree of Master of Technology or Master of Science or pursue a degree in Master of Business Administration, which enables one to acquire management skills besides the technical skills that he/she already possesses. Engineering graduates are adept in problem identification, problem solving and have an acumen for analytical analysis. This allows them to deliver excellent performance in any other profession that they choose. For example, engineering graduates, besides taking up hardcore engineering jobs, are known to do extremely well in management roles across the world. The need for engineering talent is huge today. Businesses increasingly require engineers who can design and deliver. Committed and talented minds with technical excellence have huge space for further innovations and the world is patiently waiting for their contributions in future. In year 1968, Government of India has declared 15th September as “Engineers Day” as a tribute to the greatest Engineer BharatRatna Mokshagundam Vishveshvar aiyā. Born on 15th September 1860, Dr. Vishveshvaraiya went to become India’s most prolific civil engineer, dam & bridge builder, economist, statesman and can be counted among the last century’s foremost nation-builders. Nation as well as society recalls the priceless and irreplaceable contribution of their engineers in nation building.

2. Role of Civil Engineers:

The history of engineers is as old as civilisation. As civilisation developed people began reshaping their environment with

villages, farms, watersheds, roads, ships and eventually towns. With each advancement came new challenges that required more complex and creative solutions, which were solved by experiments as well as experience. With the passage of time, there has been considerable overhauling in the system. The advent of computer & software has completely changed the scenario in infrastructure sector. Quality in construction, planning, scheduling, organising, co-ordinating, controlling, management etc has been improved and elapsed time minimised. In religious scripture, Bhagwan Vishwakarma has been enshrined as an engineer & architect of the Devlok. In Treta Yug, during departure of Shri Ram to Sri Lanka, two warriors of the Vanar Sena – Nal and Neel have showed their engineering expertise by constructing stone bridge “Shri Ram Setu” across the ocean between present day Dhanushkodi in Rameshwaram (Bharat) & Mannar (Sri Lanka). The bridge, having approximately 30-35 Km length & 3 Km width, is the unique model of ancient engineering dexterity.

Engineers play a very important role in every walk of life. They are technically skilled professionals, who are responsible for solving problems through the use of machines, devices, systems, materials and processes. They convert knowledge of basic sciences into products. Their main focus is on making things work efficiently and effectively by applying the theories and principles of sciences and mathematics to research, and develop economic solutions to technical problems. The engineer differs from scientist by the nature of their training. While the scientists try to explore the natural world and discover new knowledge about

the universe and how it works, engineers apply that knowledge to solve real problems, often with an eye toward improving cost and efficiency. Their works are the link between the perceived social needs and economic applications. They are the bridge between science and art. Engineers are the backbone of nation building and the purpose of engineering is to innovate, design, create and maintain products, system and equipment for the benefit and wellbeing of humans. They help improve living conditions for the common people. If a country fails to realise the role of engineers in her nation building and the engineers are leaving for better opportunities abroad, then the country will continue to experience collapsed buildings and bridges, substandard products, failed roads, communication failures, environmental hazards, epileptic power supply etc.

The engineers have to realise their responsibility and play an effective role in tackling today's complex issues in the nation building. To build a nation is to make it habitable for the citizens by providing social amenities, infrastructural facilities, job creation and security and many more; the engineers therefore have a very important role to play. Thus, they are duty bound to design products, machineries and plants to manufacture these products, and systems to ensure quality and efficiency. They are to design, plan and supervise construction of buildings, and ensure their safety and stability against hazards; design highways, bridges, railways and transit systems, dams, irrigation canals, power systems, ports, harbours as well as off-shore structures. Engineers should equally know that it is their duty to develop and implement improved ways to extract, process and use

raw materials; develop new raw materials that can improve product performance and take advantage of advances in technology to harness the power of the sun, the gas, the earth, atoms and electricity to supply the nation's power needs; analyse the impact of the products they develop or systems they design on the environment and the people; design ways of managing the nation's waste, converting or recycling them to useful products. Parts of their functions also include determining the cause of component failures, estimating the time and cost of completing new projects as well as maintaining the existing ones. Engineers are pivotal not only in infrastructure, but can act a catalyst in the field of trade and commerce too. In sales and management, an engineering background enables one to discuss the technical aspects of projects/products and assist in the planning, installation and product use. With such a vast and varied nature of their job, the engineers are really the foundation stone of a nation's building and their role cannot be neglected in a nation's all round progress. The engineers on their part should be proud of what they do and contribute effectively towards the growth of their country and the world at large.

3. Conclusion:

Engineers contribute to the nation's technological & industrial progress. As nations in the world are undergoing reformation and the economy is getting more modernized, consumption patterns have expanded and demand is constantly on the increase. There is therefore a growing consciousness of quality control at every level of production.

ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY OF PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract:

Collaboration between school counselors and principals is increasingly important in this accountability era. The purpose of this quantitative study was to examine the role of principal as perceived by professional school counselor and principals, both in training and practicing. While similarities were found in two categories: Managing School Personnel and School Climate, significant differences emerged in all three categories, including Parent and Community Collaboration. These findings indicate that school counselors and principals could benefit from learning more about the others' respective roles to enhance their working partnership towards increasing academic achievement.

Keywords: school counselor, principal, preparation program, collaboration, academic achievement

1. Introduction:

Coalition between the school counselor and the principal, it seems essential now to gain an understanding of how school counselors view the principal's role to complement the research conducted as to principal perceptions of the counselor's role. Williams and Wehrman (2010) stated, "School counselors have often viewed principals as adversaries rather than as collaborative partners". In order to create a trusting and effective working relationship, both must have an accurate understanding of the other's role and function in the school (Clemens et al., 2009; Williams & Wehrman, 2010).

2. Role and responsibility of professional students in nation building

This study investigated the perceptions that school counselors and principals, both in training and practicing, have of the role of the principal. In addition, the researcher examined the possibility of gender differences related to the perception of the principal's role and responsibilities. Gilligan, Lyons, and Hanmer (1989) brought forward the idea of caring relationships as a priority for women as compared to men. Thus, gender differences might emerge regarding the importance of various principal responsibilities, especially those related to interpersonal connections. To develop awareness of misunderstandings that may block effective inter-professional collaboration, the goal was to identify any gaps between the principals' stated role and

the perceptions of the principals' role identified by the study participants. Thus, the research question explored was: Is there a difference between principals and school counselors (both in training and in practice) in their perception of the role of the principal? The literature review revealed no current studies on this topic and no Instrument developed by the researchers. The Perceptions of the Principal's Roles and Responsibilities Questionnaire was developed based on the 2011 Educational Leadership Program Standards, guided by the standards and drawing from related research (e.g., Leone, Warnimont, & Zimmerman, 2009; Lynch, 2012), the researchers determined three major categories encompassing the principals' roles and corresponding responsibilities. The first category was Managing School Personnel and was comprised of responsibilities such as hiring and evaluating teachers, counselors and staff, as well as managing personnel issues and conflict resolution.

The second category of Parent and Community Collaboration included utilizing community resources and involving parents in the decision making process. The final category of school climate involved creating a safe learning environment, creating a shared vision of learning, dealing with discipline issues, acting with integrity, and making ethical decisions. To increase content validity, a former principal and current professor of an educational leadership program was invited to review the survey for accuracy. He offered several ideas for modifications that were implemented. In addition, acronbach alpha

of .80 indicated internal consistency of the instrument. Participants were sent an email consisting of the informed consent and a choice of completing the online survey or not. Participants gave consent by clicking on the link for the online survey. Participants were notified that they could discontinue their participation at any time. The researchers sent a final follow-up email two weeks later reminding potential participants that the survey was still available for completion. The survey was open to participants for a total of four weeks. Personnel in the endeavor to create a safe and effective learning environment. Of responsibilities, two emerged as significant in this category: communication and Designs can incorporate teaming with educational leadership programs to engage Principals and school counselors india logueab out the irrespectiveroles and practice collaborating. Teaching these educational leaders how to join forces boosts students' chances of progressing towards optimal success.

The unique training and specializations of the principal and the school counselor are a winning combination, if they are taught to act as a team. Educational institutions may wish to create professional development work shops that bring school counselors and principals together, enabling school counselors and principals to learn more about each other and how to collaborate. Already, principals and counselor suse research to inform their decisions, there by exhibiting a commitment to evidence-based practices and ethical decision-making. Thus, in addition to counselors assisting the principal to establish an ethical climate,

utilizing research to inform decisions can be a basis for collaboration. Educational facilities may benefit from utilizing the Principal-School Counselor Toolkit developed by the College Board's National Office for School Counselor Advocacy. This tool kit guides principals and school counselors through various activities on relationship enhancement, communication, trust and respect, leadership, and collaborative planning. In addition, the toolkit offers opportunities for advanced practice between school counselors and principals, leading them through various scenarios and problem solving simulations.

3. Conclusion

The wave of educational reform is not new, and the age of accountability is here to stay (Wilkerson, 2010; Zalaquett & Chatters, 2012). To remain current with the drive for student achievement, school counselors and principals need to recognize that they are both educational leaders. Because of this, they must form an alliance and commitment to work together towards student success. This entails learning more about each other's roles and responsibilities to forge a partnership. Principals and school counselors offer unique and specialized methods for attaining student achievement and educating them about their different perspectives augments their ability to work effectively together.

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MEDIA ROLE IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

This paper is showing the relationship between the media and education. It contains the role and importance of media in providing education, rural education and for environmental awareness. It also talks about the use of media in classroom and in the teaching learning process. This paper is representing the extensive and extreme use of media in education content and its social impact upon society because of its inherent ability to reach large number of public.

Keywords: Education, Media, social impact, environmental awareness

1. Introduction:

Education is the process of learning and knowing, which is not restricted to our school text-books. It is a holistic process and continues through our life. Even the regular happenings and events around us educate us, in one or the other way. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the existence of human beings is fruitless without education. An educated person has the ability to change the world, as he/she is brimming with confidence and assured of making the right moves.

The term media is derived from Medium, which means carrier or mode. Media denotes an item specifically designed to reach a large audience or viewers. The term was first used with the advent of newspapers and magazines. However, with the passage of time, the term broadened by the inventions of radio, TV, cinemas and Internet. In the world of today, media has become almost as necessary as food and

clothing. It is true that media is playing an outstanding role in strengthening the society. Its duty is to inform, educate and entertain the people. It helps us to know current situation around the world. The media has a strong social and cultural impact upon society. Because of its inherent ability to reach large number of public, it is widely used to convey message to build public opinion and awareness.

2. Role of Mass Media in providing Education:

Mass media :- Television programs, internet websites, feature-length films, newspapers, music tapes and CDs, magazines, billboards, radio programs: essentially, a tool/technology which is used by someone to transmit a message to a large external audience is called mass media. John Dewey stated that education could not be limited within teacher and taught without social environment. So mass media is one such potent force in the social environment of

education. Through modern electronic techniques and technologies, mass media prove that education is, really comprehensive not confined within four walls of the classroom.

Really, mass media are the educational medium for the mass and mass education. Irrespective of caste, color, geographical, sociological, economical diversities mass media prove as an important means for the education to all. Mankind gets a great deal of information from the widespread mass media i.e. newspaper, TV, radio, magazines, journals, films, etc. It is estimated that mass media may substitute the real classroom teaching in future.

3. Functions of Mass Media:

1) **Providing Information:** These media help in disseminating information for the mass. People acquire different knowledge very quickly.

2) **Providing vocational information:** Media help in providing vocational and professional information to a larger group of the community.

3) **Spreading awareness and civic responsibility:** People can be aware of different problems of the society and their role in changing society through mass media. People know their rights and duties for the nation clearly.

4) **Educational programmes:** Mass Media help in forming suitable habit for different programmes and they utilize their leisure time in a productive way. It also influences the behavior of the people through different programmes.

5) **Role as a non-formal agency:** Now in an advanced society mass media are not treated as informal agencies of education. They are called non-formal agencies due to its wide coverage of educational items in a systematic way. It is viewed that these media can substitute the classroom teaching in future.

3. Mass media for rural education and environmental awareness:

Mass media and print media and its usage play a important role for the development of rural education. Various forms of mass media such as television, radio, handy video cameras, interactive video, computer and print media (news papers, magazines bulletins, leaflets) can be used for the development of rural education. Door darshan is telecasting the latest information on agricultural education and rural development through electronic media, covering majority of rural population. The findings of various studies stated that impact of TV was more on small farmers and illiterates. They watched the agricultural programmes and adopted the recommended practices. A majority of the farmers viewed TV programmes for the sake of education.

Agriculture is the mainstay of the Indian economy and approximately half of the Indian population still gets their livelihood directly from agriculture. Most of India's poor live in rural areas and are engaged in agriculture. Climate change and food security have become burning issues in the world. Continued deforestation is a major challenge for forests and livelihood and one of the major causes of environmental degradation in India can be attributed to

rapid growth of population, which is adversely affecting the natural resources and environment. The growing trends of population and consequent demand for food, energy and housing have considerably altered land - use practices and severely degraded forest area as well as environment. These include pressure on land and forests, loss of biodiversity, rising demand for energy, global warming, climate change, water scarcity and pollution. For agricultural development, knowledge and information on farm technologies, methods and practices need to be imparted to the farmers at the right time. Mass media (electronic and print media) are playing very important role in creating environmental awareness and dissemination of new agricultural technologies among the rural people. Different information tools like radio, television and news paper are spreading awareness related to climate change and environment protection among the rural people at the faster rate than personal contact.

3. The Role of Social Media in Education Life:

These days we are living in the fast developing society which every day offers its inhabitants a great number of new possibilities. Predominantly, these unique opportunities concern the advancement of social media that have noticeably permeated the modern education world. In fact, it is not a secret that the majority of teachers and professors highly appreciate the power of these tools which lies in the ability to engage, motivate as well as to involve the students into deep contemplation and sensible discussion.

In general, the term “social media” implies the number of activities that include socializing and networking online through words, pictures and videos. To some extent, it is a two way discussion which brings people together to discover and share some information, interests as well as ideas. Admittedly, social media can range from social bookmarking, where all users have a chance to share their online libraries of links and connect to each other’s lists within a definite online community, to online collaboration spaces.

4. Implementation of Social Media into Education Life:

Nowadays, many educational establishments are beginning to embrace social media into their everyday life. It is a well- known fact that Twitter and Facebook are considered to be the fastest ways of finding information that might be of great value for all students. Remarkably, these websites can be easily used for creating a discussion in the classroom. Interestingly, it is possible to create a chat room that can be embedded later to some blog and scheduled to open at a specified time. Actually, all teachers can easily pull new stories from any of these online sources and the students can put any questions in order to develop the further discussion of the previously downloaded article. Speaking about various blogs, they can be utilized to encourage creative writing and to enrich grammar skills. Thus, the professors here are welcome to suggest their requirements for writing projects that are to be fulfilled by the students within certain deadlines. On the whole, one of the biggest assets of each social media tool lies in bringing together the students of all ages to

help them with all types of assignments, starting with the homework and finishing with different researches. It is worth mentioning that such phenomenon as geo-tagging has a great future perspective in education life, owing to the fact that it can be used to target and find necessary data about the places that are being studied. In addition, it has been scientifically proven that social media can assist the students in solving their engagement crisis. Indeed, the lack of engagement has become the main reason for students' expulsion both from the course and college. In this case, social media engages them into close communication and collaboration with their instructors so that the studying process is properly maintained.

5. The Use of Media in Teaching – Learning Process:

Learning is a process to acquire knowledge. It needs hard work and sometimes will make students frustrated and get bored, so that they lose their attention to a lesson. In this case, the use of media in teaching- learning process is needed to attract students' attention and to make teaching- learning activities more interesting and also effective. The use of media in teaching- learning process is not a new thing. Many teachers know that media will be helpful. Media give students something new, but not all of teachers know how to implement it correctly, so sometimes media disturb learning process instead of helping students in learning process. This situation causes a problem. The use of media is questioning whether it really helps teaching- learning activities or not. Based on that assumption, the writer wants to find out the fact of the use of media in teaching- learning process,

whether media can help teaching- learning process or not. By reading this article, readers will get a real experience of the use of media, which can help learning process. Besides, they will also know some obstacles that may arise from the use of media, how to overcome them, and detail example of how to conduct teaching- learning process by using media, especially globe and map. This article will provide an interview of a teacher's experience in implementing media for teaching social studies.

Usually use of media is very useful to teach social studies by this we can use pictures from encyclopedia or else, a globe, a map, and internet to teach social studies. the students had to find all-important information including the map, flag, landmark, famous buildings, mountains, traditions, etc. By using media in teaching, students' improvement can be seen clearly.

6. The Importance of Media in the Classroom:

Media in the classroom engage students in learning and provide a richer experience. Media are useful tools for illustrating a lesson, allowing students to see examples of what they are learning. Interactive media such as Smart Boards allow students to move items on a screen for illustrative purposes. Students view media as exciting learning aids, making learning entertaining and less monotonous, according to the report "Benefits and Risks of Media and Technology in the Classroom "from the UCLA Office of Instructional Development.

Appeal to Multiple Learning Styles:

Media appeal to visual, auditory and kinesthetic learners. Students can watch a

movie, listen to music or interact with digital media on an interactive Smart Board. Effective teachers do not rely on teaching students in merely one style but use a variety of styles to reach the greatest number of students. Providing a rich learning experience through classroom media keeps students focused and engaged in learning.

Creates an Authentic Learning Experience:

Using newspapers, brochures, job application forms and news broadcasts provides authentic opportunities for students to learn using real-world media. This method simulates real-life experiences in which students must read, evaluate and interpret information based on items that they need in their daily lives. When students use objects from the real world, they can see the connection between what they learn in school and how they can use the knowledge as a member of society.

Strengthens Critical-Thinking Skills:

Teachers can use media to hone critical-thinking skills. Students can write about a song, interpret a movie or interpret a news broadcast. Teachers can use the media to ask probing questions and facilitate discussions that extend beyond basic comprehension questions. Teachers can also create projects in which students develop their own media, using classroom media as a model. This hands-on activity challenges students to formulate media, using their own creativity and interpretations from classroom media.

Teaches Students to Use Media:

Using media in the classroom teaches students how to use and care for resources to

further their education. Students not only learn how to use the Internet, a dictionary or a newspaper for information, but they also learn how to care for and protect the items they use, according to the Center for Media Literacy. Students can also learn how to determine the value of media and learn methods to contribute to society, producing their own media.

9. Conclusion: The media has the power of educating people, the good and the bad. Since it affect the eyes, the ears and the mind simultaneously nothing can overcome the influence of the media. The media in the advanced society should perform a noble mission of enlightening people and discourage sectarian, communal and divisive trends. Media integration is consistently referred to as a relatively new phenomenon in education. Although complete media integration is not yet commonplace in classrooms throughout the country, media's use in the classroom, much like that of technology, is seemingly old hat Although "movie day in the classroom" has shifted from slides and projectors to DVDs and YouTube as a result of rapidly- changing technologies in the 21st century, media use in the classroom remains prevalent none the less .Hardly a country in the world is spared controversy in education, but when one looks behind the sometimes anarchic scenes, there is a lot about which to be optimistic and hopeful.

Traditionally, the mass media and education have enjoyed a love-hate relationship. On one hand television and newspapers particularly, have provided extensive and extremely useful education content. On the other, however, their newsrooms never seem

to hesitate when controversy rears its ugly head. The power of media is so extensive and huge; it can be used to educate people with very little cost.

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ACCOUNTABILITY OF STUDENTS IN NATION BUILDING

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Abstract

Students are the beacon of the future of a nation. No society has ever evolved without the right guidance and social engagement of the student fraternity. All the great social reformers who we think of today are or were great socially attached students. We can never hope for successful country if there are no educated people and policy for better education. They are the root of Nation Development. Every minute contribution is counted when it is directed to the appropriate individual.

Keywords: Students, Fraternity, Development, Nation.

1. Introduction:

Students, the future of a nation, play a very vital role in nation building. Every individual countryman can play its role in nation building by doing his duties in right manner. One should be sincere about his duties not only for self but also in the prospects of the nation. As we all know that our life is very short and we have a lot to do for our society, our nation and for the whole world. Mainly two duties are there which we have to play sincerely. One is to do the maximum efforts in the shortest possible duration without taking stress and secondly is whatever we may be in the society; we have to do our work with sincere efforts. As we know that the future of country or of a nation fully depends upon its citizens so there is a great need of healthy minds. This is possible only when the discipline is inculcated by making the students aware of their duties and responsibilities. For making young generation an integral part of nation building, the seeds of discipline must be sown in their minds through moral values. Whatever

knowledge is being acquired by the student's that should be utilized for the betterment of self, society and the nation development.

2. Student's accountability

The educational values should help them to mould themselves into dutiful citizens. As we all know that academic discipline deserves serious consideration. Students should not mislead their self by indulging in the activities which may take them away from their destination. Students must be cautious and sincere about their future. They should know their role in the society. Mainly students deal with study, as duty. This very duty of process of learning brings knowledge and off course social and cultural, Traditional touch amongst them. This very tradition and culture remain in their heart till they get older and become a sincere part of the nation and society. Student's life gives a lot the children by virtue of taking part in co-curricular activities and many other activities. These very habits help children to inculcate patriotic touch amongst them. Maintaining the dignity of student's life brings a lot in

them. In early pre-independent India where students were motivated to play their role in the national struggle for freedom movements by leaving study aside. They have been called by the freedom fighters time to time for their participation in getting country free from the rule of British. At the time of quit India movement was the major event in this regard. Lakhs and lakhs of students took part in this movement by leaving their studies aside. It was a sincere participation of students in national interest. Youth Indians felt proud of being a part of this movement. They have been treated as key players in quit India movement. Even today students can play the same role by following the rules and regulations in various concerns. India gained independence; at this point, the students were under intense pressure to rebuild the country. It was not an easy task to complete in such a short period of time. The issues that India faced after independence were extremely difficult to resolve. It was time to draught legislation and make major changes for the good of the people. Things were not easy to settle in this case. The entire nation was behind the young strength. It is a source of pride that students played an important role in the national reconstruction of liberated India. This was a period of crisis. and disaster for free India, but students shown the use of their potential for nation building. Especially the young brigade of the border part of free India played a prominent role by providing the relief and shelter to the needy persons. Students have used their abilities to benefit both society and the nation. They frequently assisted state and civil authorities in a variety of ways, including maintaining law and order, communal harmony, peace, services

required as volunteers, vaccination programmes, immunization, pulse polio drops, floods, earthquakes, cyclones, fires, accidents, elections, literacy campaigns, including adult literacy and census, by holding rallies, awareness programmes, exhibitions, direct participation, financial contributions, and by providing medicine. Every minute contribution is counted when it is directed to the appropriate individual.

Role of students in clean and dirt free politics is a major challenge now. Most of we feel that the political scenario of today's is not so pollution free. People contribute to their nation by providing taxes and all but this important sum goes in vain by virtue of insincere efforts and improper planning. Students should not indulge in such activities. In India politics have an impact on the minds of the young generation. They are interacted towards the power of politics.

The students should realize that this is the best time for them to study when their mind is fresh and when they are free from the stress and strain of life which often overtakes the grow-up minds. They can utilize their strength for the betterment of the society either by doing a good turn or by through some NGO's. They can contribute by doing their duties faithfully and sincerely. Students can share their problems with teachers of their institution. They can resolve all their matters with the authority concerns. They should help in maintaining the dignity of the institution. They should avoid strike and other ways of means to resolve problems. Maintaining discipline in the institution plays a very vital role in maintaining law and order. Educational bodies try avoiding having

elections in their institutions, this leads to dirty political scenario in the institution

3. Conclusion: Students play a crucial part in the development of a country. They are the important members of society. They might carry out their global duty. They might offer assistance in any form. By embracing

discipline, students must uphold their dignity. They need to focus on taking aim. They have the potential to build ideals through making sincere contributions to society as well as the institution. I hope they keep up the custom of being an honest member of society.

ROLE OF TEACHERS IN NATION BUILDING WITH FUTURE ICONS

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Abstract:

Teacher is a maker of man. He is foundation of all Education, and thus of the whole civilization of mankind, present and future. No nation reconstruction is possible without the active cooperation of the teacher. Today, education is increasingly being regarded as the major weapon in the crusade for supremacy on the economic front. Television, telephone and computers are reshaping practically every walk of life, including education. The classrooms of tomorrow could be entirely different from those of today. The teachers will play a very significant role. It would not only be complex but also full of challenges, because dependence on the teacher will gradually diminish for an individual learner. The television, telephone and computer will take over and encourage self-learning. Distance education may reduce the need to devote much time within the four walls of the classroom. New techniques of assessment will be available to the realistic assessment would also provide an opportunity for self-directed improvement by the learner, which is rare in the existing system.

Keywords: Role of Teacher-educator, nation building, teacher profession, teacher education.

1. Introduction:

Education is the ultimate realm of the homosapiens. It is a process aimed at socialized and humanizing individual citizen through their life from birth till death. It is institutionalized and formal for a specific period but lifelong and suited to ones environment, ability, interest, aspiration, aptitude etc. and carried on preferably outside the institutional premises through life non-formally and informally and more significant and rewarding. Education is a process of enlightenment and empowerment of the individual for achievement of better and

high quality of life. The Education Commission (1964-66) has emphatically opined that “The quality and competence and character of teachers to be the most significant factor influencing the quality of education and its contribution to National development.”

2. The importance of the teacher in national life:

The importance of the teacher in national life cannot be over-emphasized. It is he who influences the immature minds of the youth. He treats and tries to mould the living stuff into various forms. The future

of the nation is fashioned by him through the process of education. A nation trying to march ahead on the roads to progress can leave the education of her sons and daughter in the hands of incompetent teachers only at its own risk. "The world of tomorrow will be born from the schools of today" says M.L Jacks. In this way, teachers, indeed, is the true builder of the nation.

In the past, teachers were held by all in the highest esteem. Even kings and emperors used to look upto them for guidance and advice in hours of crisis. As a matter of fact, teachers were the trustees of common welfare. Teachers in those days were the true benefactors of society. History is full of examples which clearly show that great decisions of vital importance to the whole nation were taken on the directions of the teachers. Such was the importance which was enjoyed by teachers in the past.

A nation is built by its citizens, citizens are moulded by teachers and teachers are made by teacher-educators. Chanakya has rightly stated, "Teacher is the maker of nation" So for the development of the country, it is very important to have good teachers and good teachers can be produced only if we have a good system of teacher education and dedicated and efficient teacher-educators.

3. A nation builder:

The teacher can be rightly called a nation builder. Teachers through their perseverance love and sacrifices have shown us the right path in which great men have built our nation. It is our dear

teachers who mould our character, our personality and show us the right direction which leads us to our final destination.

Flourishing national development and a society truly prosperous with knowledge all begins from its teachers. While the role of knowledge and a skilled society with visions and aspirations in the success of a nation cannot be stressed enough, it should also be remembered that knowledge cannot be acquired if it is not sought and received through the help of the teacher. This is why everyone should put efforts into seeking as much knowledge as possible, and appreciate the teacher's importance in guiding us and the generations to come, to become knowledgeable and morally upright people. Knowledge received without a teacher's guidance can be compared to a blind man walking without his stick. Because of this, teachers need to have a high level of commitment towards their duties and responsibilities which have been entrusted to them. The teacher is a judge who gives marks and ratings. He differentiates children on the basis of their intellectual and often social skills in preparation for the social and occupational roles which they eventually play.

4. A multi-faceted task:

The role of the teacher is a multi-faceted one comprising academic, pedagogical and social roles. Academic roles comprise teaching, counseling and supervisory roles while pedagogical roles include instructional, evaluation and facilitating roles. As a facilitator of learning, the teacher is involved in

motivating pupils to learn, maintaining control in the classroom and the school in general, and creating a conducive environment for learning to take place. Social roles of the teacher includes among others socializing roles which is preparing pupils to participate in the way of life of the society; others include reference roles, detective roles, parent surrogate (or substitute parent), confidants and affectionate roles.

No other personality can have an influence more profound than that of a teacher. Students are deeply affected by the teacher's love and affection, his character, his competence, and his moral commitment. A popular teacher becomes a model for his students. The students try to follow their teacher in his manners, customs, etiquette, style of conversation and his get up. He is their ideal. He can lead them anywhere. During their early education, the students tend to determine their aims in life and their future plans, in consultation with their teachers.

5. Teacher should play a cardinal role:

Teachers therefore, have to play a cardinal role in the building up of the character of the next generation. It is a fact that a civilization cannot rise out of a Civilization finds a concrete shape in the practical behaviour of a nation, based on these principles and concepts. Once the practical aspect is gone, the civilization also disappears and can only be studied through its remnants preserved in museums and chronicles. This necessitates the provision of a learning atmosphere throbbing with life in our educational

institutions through the presence of the teacher, with a view to infuse confidence in our students and to enable them to be proud of their culture, to respect their national character and national emblems, and to ornament themselves with societal conduct and morals. They should stand firm on the centuries old foundations of their cultural tradition and at the same time should establish standards of excellence in their

Teachers are the future builders of our country, they are the providers of knowledge and wisdom. They are the basic source of education for most of the people of the country and they are the ones who build the future of the nation. The teachers can very easily decide what they want the nation to look like and educate the masses accordingly. They have the ability and the strength to fight the odds and make India a powerful and a well educated country.

Teachers have a vital role in nation building because the future is totally in their hands. They choose to be the fortune builders of the country and if you really want to know how important teachers are for their country, try imagining a nation without them. It will only be a nation of utter chaos where nobody would step up to make sure the kids get the best education and the knowledge to sustain a good and healthy life. The nation will no longer be able to progress and the population will be sick. Here are a few characteristics of the roles that our teachers play every single day- Making the children ready for a challenging life - it starts at a very early age, the teachers take the kids away from their parents for a few hours and teach

them in a total different environment.

6. Literacy and wisdom: The teachers not only make the child literate so that he/she can earn enough to have a normal lifestyle, they also provide words of wisdom every day which shape the personality of the child. Many children are influenced by their teachers more than the parents. A teacher is mostly selfless and believes in dissipating whatever information he/she can to make the kid wiser than yesterday.

7. A friend, philosopher and guide: Today we can see that teachers have moved on from the basic image of a strict teacher, they have become much more for their students. They provide a friendly shoulder to cry on when the kid is in a problem, they tell about the philosophies of life so that the child could take lessons and apply to his/her own life and they guide the child to follow the right path. The teachers have the courage to push the kid to do what they want to, even if it has never been done before.

8. Well-wishers: No other job makes a person worried if a child's parent is divorced, a drunk or a wife abuser. Teachers are the ones who have full knowledge of the child's life, the environment back home, his mindset and his capabilities. They always try and strike a balance between all of these things and make sure that the kid's future doesn't get affected in a bad way.

9. Nation builder: A nation comprises of the children way more than adults. The children are the future and the teachers are the ones who are getting them ready for their task. With optimum education,

wisdom, exposure and resources, the teachers are building the nation for tomorrow brick by brick and the foundation is so solid that the nation will only grow upwards.

10. Teaching as a profession:

Teaching as a profession is probably the most challenging because it combines all the other professions in order to help a child grow. One has to have good communication skills, managerial skills, reading and writing skills, storytelling skills, everything. The teachers have selflessly and courageously chosen the path where they will always be working for the mankind and for its good. Not everybody has the heart to do it. The leaders of today are getting the leaders of tomorrow ready.

Times have now under gone, a tremendous change. teachers have lost their old glory. they are now looked down upon in society. Their economic condition is simply miserable. Even the Government peons are better off than the primary, junior, and even High School teachers. We all know that economically our country is backward and the standard of living of the masses is low. In a country of such low standards, the teacher stands at the lowest rung of the ladder.

Besides this, we live in a materialistic world. Only those command respect and position in society who have enough money. The teacher, being poor, does not enjoy any prestige in society. He suffers in many other ways also. It has become a common feeling with the people that, one who fails everywhere else and has been

rejected at all other places, becomes teacher as a last resort. In this way also teaching profession has been down-graded, their services are considered non essential and thus they do not get necessary recognition from society.

11. Education is a complicated process:

Education is a complicated process. Not only the teacher, but so many other agencies also take part in educating the youth. We are all aware of the influence of the cinema on the minds of children. How quickly they imitate the ways of dressing, walking and talking of their favorite stars is a matter of common experience. The television has also become quite popular. This too has its influence on children. Various other public activities like elections and meetings of political parties also serve as agencies of education. Rather, he has a very limited influence.

12. Conclusion:

Today, education is increasingly being regarded as the major weapon in the crusade for supremacy on the economic front. Television, telephone and computers are reshaping practically every walk of life, including education. The classrooms of tomorrow could be entirely different from those of today. The teachers will play a very significant role. It would not only be complex but also full of challenges, because dependence on the teacher will gradually diminish for an individual learner. The television, telephone and computer will take over and encourage self-learning.

However, the situation is not so depressing for a teacher. The importance of the role of the teachers as an agent of change, promoting understanding and tolerance has become more obvious and is likely to become even more critical in the 21st century. This places enormous responsibilities on teachers who participate in the molding of the character and minds of the new generation.

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STUDY OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Women entrepreneurship is gaining importance in India in the wake of economic liberalization and globalization. “In Indian mythology, woman is an incarnation of Shakthi-the Goddess of Power. We believe women empowerment is vital to our development” Honorable Prime Minister of India. The policy and institutional framework for developing entrepreneurial skills, providing vocation education and training has widened the horizon for economic empowerment of women. However, women constitute only one third of the economic enterprises. In today’s world, women entrepreneurs are playing very vital role and they have become important part of the global business environment and it’s really important for the sustained economic development and social progress. In India, though women are playing key role in the society, but still their entrepreneurial ability has not been properly tapped due to the lower status of women in the society. The main purpose of this paper is to find out the status of women entrepreneurs in India. This paper includes rationale grounds behind the women entrepreneurship. Another main purpose of this paper is to analyze policies of Indian government for women and also to analyze that are those policies adequate for the growth of women entrepreneurship. Main reasons for women to become an entrepreneur, the institutions that are serving the women to put their views into action are also included in this study. On the basis of this study some suggestions are given to encourage spirit of women entrepreneurship to become a successful entrepreneur.

Keywords: Women Entrepreneurs, Government support schemes

1. Introduction:

In Indian mythology, woman is an incarnation of Shakthi-the Goddess of Power. We believe women empowerment is vital to our development” Honorable Prime Minister of India, Women entrepreneurship is gaining importance in India in the wake of economic liberalization and globalization. The policy and institutional framework for

developing entrepreneurial skills, providing vocation education and training has widened the horizon for economic empowerment of women. However, women constitute only one third of the economic enterprises. Women Entrepreneurs may be define as the women or a group of women who commence and operate a business venture. . Like a male entrepreneurs a women

entrepreneur has many functions. They should explore the prospects of starting new enterprise; undertake risks, introduction of new innovations, coordination, administration and control of business and providing effective leadership in all aspects of business. Government of India has described women entrepreneurs as an enterprise/venture owned and controlled by women having at least financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of employment generated in the organization to women.

Women Entrepreneurs are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. The hidden business potentials of women have been increasing with the growing sensitivity to the role and economic status in the society. The knowledge, Skill and compliance in business are the core reasons for women to come forward into business ventures. Women entrepreneurs engage in business due to push and pull factors which give confidence to women to have a Self-sufficient occupation and stands on their feet. Logic towards independent decision-making on their life and career is the motivational factor behind this insists on Women Entrepreneur is a person who accepts challenging role to meet her personal desires and turn out to be economically independent. A strong desire to do enormous positive is an integral quality of entrepreneurial women, who is competent of contributing values in both family and social life. With the introduction of media, women are conscious of their own qualities, rights and also the work situations.

2. Literature Review:

Das, 2000 performed a study on women entrepreneurs of SMEs in two states of India, viz, Tamil Nadu and Kerala. The initial problems faced by women entrepreneurs are quite similar to those faced by women in western countries. However, Indian women entrepreneurs faced lower level of work-family conflict and are also found to differ from their counterparts in western countries on the basis of reasons for starting and succeeding in business. Similar trends are also found in other Asian countries such as Indonesia and Singapore. Again the statistics showed that the proportion of business setup and operated by women is much lower than the figures found in western countries.

Singh, 2008, identifies the reasons & influencing factors behind entry of women in entrepreneurship. He explained the characteristics of their businesses in Indian context and also obstacles & challenges. He mentioned the obstacles in the growth of women entrepreneurship are mainly lack of interaction with successful entrepreneurs, social un-acceptance as women entrepreneurs, family responsibility, gender discrimination, missing network, low priority given by bankers to provide loan to women entrepreneurs. He suggested the remedial measures like promoting micro enterprises, unlocking institutional frame work, projecting & pulling to grow & support the winners etc. The study advocates for ensuring synergy among women related ministry, economic ministry & social & welfare development ministry of the Government of India.

3. Women Entrepreneurship in India:

For any developing country, Women entrepreneurs play the vital role particularly in terms of their contribution to the economic development. Women entrepreneurship has been recognized as an important source of economic growth. By establishing their new venture women entrepreneurs generate new jobs for themselves and others and also provide society with different solutions to management, organization and business problems. However, they still represent minority as women entrepreneurs, especially in India. Women entrepreneurs often face gender-based barriers to starting and growing their businesses, like discriminatory property, matrimonial and inheritance laws and/or cultural practices; lack of access to formal finance mechanisms limited mobility and access to information and networks, etc. Women's entrepreneurship can make a particularly strong contribution to the economic well-being of the family and communities, poverty reduction and women's empowerment. Thus, governments across the world as well as various developmental organizations are actively assisting and promoting women entrepreneurs through various schemes, incentives and promotional measures.

Over the past few decades women are coming out of the boundaries of houses and proving their ability and competencies in the business world. Today the roles of women are not confined to the traditional role of a mother or a housewife. The role of modern women is much wider than, what it was previously. A woman has to play multiple

roles, besides playing the role of housewife/mother/daughter, she has to play different roles in community in the social settings simultaneously. Because of Indian culture traditional customs women, even after 63 years of independence, are facing bias. This has adversely affected the status of Indian business women.

4. Women entrepreneurs can be broadly categorized into five categories:

◆ **Affluent entrepreneurs** – These are daughters and wives of wealthy businessmen. These women have the financial aid and the necessary resources to start a new enterprise and take business risks.

◆ **Pull factors** – These are educated women living in urban areas with or without work experience who take the risk of a new enterprise with the help of financial institutions and commercial banks. These women take up a new business as a challenge in order to be financially independent.

◆ **Push factors** – These women take up some business activity in order to overcome financial difficulties. Generally widows and single women manage an existing family business or develop a new business due to difficult family situations.

◆ **Rural entrepreneurs** – These women belong to rural areas and choose a business suiting their resources and knowledge. Business carried out involves low investment, minimum risk and does not require any special skills.

◆ **Self-employed entrepreneurs** – They are uneducated women who fall below the poverty line. They choose tiny and small enterprise which are convenient to manage and adequate for the sustenance of her family.

6. Conclusion

Self-employed women should be encouraged to employ on a part-time or full-time basis at least one person so that they have more time for their family and can take interest in other occupations, actively participate in decision-making bodies. Training, advice or consultancy targeted solely or mainly at women entrepreneurs Start up programmes for women, particularly those returning to the labour market. Special targeting of women in general campaigns to boost levels of entrepreneurship. Equal opportunities policies aiming for equal access for women to services. Need to have network with other firms to generate business and access informal advice. Encouraging and assisting relevant business support initiatives.

Empowering women entrepreneurs is crucial for achieving the goals of sustainable development and the bottlenecks hindering their growth must be reduced to enable full participation in the business. Apart from training programs Newsletters, mentoring, trade fairs and exhibitions also can be a source for entrepreneurial development. As a result, the desired outcomes of the business are quickly achieved and more of remunerative business opportunities are found. Therefore promoting entrepreneurship among Indian women is certainly a short-cut to rapid economic

growth and development. Let us try to eradicate all kinds of gender bias and thus allow women to be a great entrepreneur at par with men.

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